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*Enhanced Citation Intent Classification with Population-Based Training,
Ensemble Strategies, and Language Models*

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**Enhanced Citation Intent Classification with
Population-Based Training, Ensemble Strategies, and
Language Models**

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Abstract

With the growing volume of scholarly literature produced and published each year, the need for precise and reliable tools aimed at classifying the intent of an author when he/she cites another work has become evident for bibliometric analyses and research assessments. This dissertation thereby explores various possibilities within the field of Citation Intent Classification (CIC) to develop such tools, mainly analyzing the applicability of Population-Based Training (PBT), Ensemble Strategies, and advanced Language Models (LMs). This study introduces a novel methodological framework for the CIC task that leverages the strengths of three Pre-Trained Language Models (PLMs): SciBERT, Galactica, and XLNet.

The first part of the empirical study focuses on enhancing the performance of such models through the integration of Population-Based Training (PBT) and fine-grained evaluations. This approach fine-tunes the models on the CIC task while dynamically searching and optimizing their hyperparameters, finally demonstrating some relevant improvements in model efficacy and adaptability to the complex language of scientific discourse. Instead, the second part of the framework introduces a Binary-based Ensemble Strategy that leverages the base versions of the aforementioned PLMs. This ensemble approach aims to harness the complementary strengths of each model while addressing their potential biases through a Meta-Classifier head. By implementing such a meta-classification layer on top of these diverse models, this research showcases the synergistic potential of ensemble techniques in elevating classification accuracy beyond the capabilities of individual models, or of base fine-tuning methodologies. Through extensive experiments conducted on the SciCite dataset, this work not only advances the State-Of-The-Art (SOTA) in the CIC task, but also sheds light on the potential of combining diverse LMs and fine-tuning strategies to address the complexities of academic discourse.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Introduction

The goal of this work is to explore whether the role of advanced hyperparameter optimization methodologies and ensemble strategies may be a key determinant in improving the overall performances and robustness of Language Models (LMs)¹ when employed for the Citation Intent Classification task. Identifying the intent behind citations has become particularly important in recent years. Indeed, with the advent of digital technologies and the proliferation of scientific literature, new questions have arisen within the scientific community. Many of these have led to discussions revolving around the *Open Science* movement, and some are directly focused on designing new and meaningful metrics and procedures for research assessment. Specifically, the application of citation analysis and bibliometrics as tools for evaluating research, and consequently for allocating research funding, occupies a central position in this process (Pride, 2022).

Many researchers problematized the use of bibliometrics in research assessment, in particular shedding light on the paradoxical nature hidden behind the abuse of metrics involving citation counts as a proxy for research assessment. Indeed, Pride (2022; Pride and Knoth, 2017) states that there are no sufficient evidences to demonstrate a connection between research quality and citation rates, while Wallin (2005) accounts for the widespread use of the Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and the h-index - two bibliometrics-based mainly on citation counts - as research quality proxies. Such citation count-based metrics are used to evaluate researchers, publications, and journals (Li and Ho, 2008), providing no meaningful differentiation behind different kinds of citations. Indeed, some citations may indicate the reuse of a methodology, while others may merely serve as an acknowledgment of a prior work (Cohen et al., 2019). It is thus clear that differentiating the nature of citations is instrumental in providing more comprehensive and meaningful analyses in research assessment-related fields (Teufel et al., 2006; Pride and Knoth, 2017; Small, 2018).

“Without an understanding of why citations are occurring, [...] bibliometric measures that rely on citation counts alone are potentially missing a large amount of information. It is therefore more interesting and valuable to know not only that a piece of work was cited, but also the reason for this citation” (Pride and Knoth, 2020).

¹ Within this thesis “Language Models (LMs)” is used to define also PLMs. For a brief distinction see **Appendix B.2**.

Figure 1. *ArXiv Yearly Submissions.*

Total number of submissions on ArXiv per year [August 1991- February 2024].

Available at: https://arxiv.org/stats/monthly_submissions

Another area in which citations are largely employed is the domain of information retrieval. In particular, as highlighted by Pride (2022), “*the sheer volume of new research now being produced on an annual basis is far beyond the capacity of a single researcher to investigate even the narrowest of domains without effective search tools*” (see **Figure 1**).

Thereby, developing tools capable of meaningfully retrieving influential papers, thus not solely based on citation counts, is fundamentally important for both promoting more conscious research (Ritchie, 2009), but also in reducing the impact of the so-called *Matthew effect*, according to which the more a paper is cited, the more citations it will likely receive (Merton, 1968). Finally, citations occupy a central role also in studies related to the evolution of scientific fields (Jurgens et al., 2018), where are employed to construct citation networks and to frame different periods.

Nevertheless, it is clear how citations play a pivotal role within academic discourse and research assessment practices, thus providing the basic reason behind the experiments discussed within this thesis.

1.1. Methodological Shift in Citation Intent Classification

Ascertained the need to produce meaningful classifications of citation intents to push forward the academic discourse under the different perspectives delineated in the preceding section, it is interesting to observe the historical approaches to this task, which will be better delineated in Chapter 2. Indeed, the evolution of the Citation Intent Classification (CIC) task has gone hand in hand with the available methodologies within the domain of Artificial Intelligence (AI), and in particular with Natural Language Processing (NLP) related techniques. With the advent of new and sophisticated computational models, it is today easier to automatically discern citations according to their inherent semantics, but many possibilities are still available to obtain more reliable and accurate classifications.

Together with astonishing architectures, many new strategies have been developed within the field, and different ways to optimize the resulting models have been devised. Thereby, this evolution does not solely rely on model architectures, but also on innovative approaches to combine the strengths of different models, and to push them beyond their limits by carefully optimizing their parameters in strategic and synchronous ways. Ensemble Strategies in classification problems propose the aggregation of many weak learners to produce a more robust classification model (Salunkhe and Mali, 2016; Mohammed and Kora, 2023), thus leveraging the strengths and mitigating the weaknesses of multiple baseline classifiers (Jia et al., 2023). Such strategies, together with the application of Nature-Inspired Optimization Algorithms (Kumar et al., 2022), derived from the principles of biological evolution - reproduction and survival of the fittest - to Neural Network hyperparameter search spaces (Jaderberg et al., 2017), led to a new plethora of available possibilities within the field of Citation Intent Classification.

The methodological shift in Citation Intent Classification reflects the broader trends in AI and NLP. From the early days of heuristic rules to the current era of sophisticated LMs and evolutionary optimization, the field has witnessed remarkable progress. These introductory concepts lay the groundwork for understanding the complexities and challenges that define this research. While this dissertation will delve deeper into some specific methodologies and their applications, it will also become clearer and clearer that the field of Citation Intent Classification holds even greater potential for innovation and discovery.

1.2. Citations & Citation Intents - a Bird's-Eye View

Citation are conceptual directional links that go from a citing bibliographic entity to a cited bibliographic entity, and are created whenever the author of a published study acknowledges other studies in its bibliographic references (Peroni and Shotton, 2019), enabling researchers to build upon previous work and thereby contributing in providing new insights in their fields. By serving as essential tools for research assessment and information retrieval, they contribute to a more reliable and accessible research paradigm, but also enhances the credibility of the citing work by grounding it in established research. Furthermore, in the Open Science domain, citations play a central role in promoting transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility. With the acknowledgment of sources, researchers adhere to ethical standards thus fostering a culture of openness and accountability, and thereby facilitating the traceability of research ideas and methodologies, together with enabling the replication of studies and the verification of findings, which are all core pillars within the Open Science community.

As stated above, citations serve as tools for research assessment, offering quantitative and qualitative insights into the impact and relevance of scholarly work. Traditional bibliometric indicators that rely on citation counts, such as the Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and the h-index, all suffer from the limitation of treating all citations equally (Teufel et al., 2006; Pride and Knoth, 2017), without discerning the importance and different roles that these may have in a research work. The same limitation applies also to citation databases such as Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science (WoS). These databases highly rely on citation counts - together with recency and relevance to the initial search term - as one of the main factors to rank the results provided by their search engines (Pride, 2022). Finally, in the context of information retrieval, understanding citation intents enhances search algorithms by enabling a more precise and context-aware retrieval of scholarly literature. This not only helps researchers in navigating the wide amount of academic publications, but also supports the identification of seminal works and emerging trends within disciplines, without reiterating and increasing the incidence of the above mentioned *Matthew Effect* (Pride, 2022).

By integrating citation intents into research assessment and information retrieval processes and tools, it is possible to move toward a more reliable and accessible research paradigm. This approach

aligns with the goals of the Open Science movement, emphasizing the importance of clarity and openness, as well as the responsible use of bibliometrics. In doing so, it promises to enrich scholarly communication, foster innovation, and facilitate a more informed and collaborative research landscape.

Finally, to provide a comprehensive yet easy example of what Citation Intents are, and of how these may be categorized, it is reported below a table presenting some examples and their categorizations (see **Table 1**). Such table employs the schema defined by Cohan and colleagues (2019) in their SciCite dataset, which will be detailed in Chapter 2.

Intent category	Definition	Example
Background information	The citation states, mentions, or points to the background information giving more context about a problem, concept, approach, topic, or importance of the problem in the field.	Recent evidence suggests that co-occurring alexithymia may explain deficits [12]. Locally high-temperature melting regions can act as permanent termination sites [6-9]. One line of work is focused on changing the objective function (Mao et al., 2016).
Method	Making use of a method, tool, approach or dataset	Fold differences were calculated by a mathematical model described in [4]. We use Orthogonal Initialization (Saxe et al., 2014)
Result comparison	Comparison of the paper's results/findings with the results/findings of other work	Weighted measurements were superior to T2-weighted contrast imaging which was in accordance with former studies [25-27] Similar results to our study were reported in the study of Lee et al (2010).

Table 1. *Citation Intents Examples.*

The table presents seven examples of annotated citation intents, with a brief yet comprehensive description of classes. Image taken from Cohan et al. (2019).

1.3. Research Objectives & Thesis Structure

This research, as briefly introduced at the beginning of this chapter, is guided by the will to extend the empirical landscape of the Citation Intent Classification (CIC) task, by providing different methodologies w.r.t. the ones yet proposed and analyzed within the field. The ultimate goal of this study is thereby the exploration of the possibilities that derive by the integration of advanced hyperparameter optimization algorithms and ensemble strategies with LMs, with the aim to understand whether such techniques may be a key determinant in improving the overall performances and efficacies of classifiers for the CIC task.

By the exploration of hyperparameter optimization strategies, this study takes into account the complex landscape where the optimal configuration of model parameters can significantly influence the model's ability to learn and generalize from the data. Additionally, with the experiments on

ensemble strategies, this work further emphasizes the need for robustness and reliability within this domain, and explores some new possibilities to enhance both performances and understandability of the outputs. A collective approach that leverages the strengths of multiple models and combines them with both human evaluations and metaclassifier heads aimed at correcting biases of the base models, may potentially offer more reliable and robust predictive capabilities compared to the ones obtained by means of a single Language Model.

Furthermore, a key concern that limits and reduces the adoption of the tools for citation intent classification is the low explainability of the results. Explainability is an additional value that this research aims to add to the Citation Intent Classification domain, and such presumption is rooted in the belief that diversity in model perspectives can enhance the overall interpretative quality of the classification task, potentially leading to groundbreaking insights into citation intents. Thereby, this research paves the way for further studies on Explainable-AI, providing the ground base for more reliable and explainable research - suggesting for further possibilities involving feature ablation studies and structured data sources - even within the nuances of Language Models predictions².

Finally, this work is part of the GraspOS project, which will be briefly explained later, in Chapter 6, and it is ultimately aimed at developing a robust, reliable, and explainable tool for the automatic classification of citation intents. All the experiments carried out have been supported by *OpenCitations*³, an independent and not-for-profit infrastructure organization for open scholarship, dedicated to the publication of open bibliographic and citation data as Linked Open Data by the use of Semantic Web technologies (Peroni and Shotton, 2019).

1.3.1. Thesis structure

This work contributes to the scholarly community by offering a comprehensive analysis of the current state of CIC research, highlighting the gaps and opportunities for further exploration. The innovative methodologies proposed here, particularly the application of advanced LMs and fine-tuning strategies, represent a significant leap forward in the classification of citation intents.

² Extremely difficult to understand and explain because of the vast amount of parameters and training data.

³ <https://opencitations.net/>

This thesis is structured as follows. Chapter 2 provides an overview of the Citation Intent Classification task, highlighting challenges and possibilities within the domain. This section also presents a brief review of the past and current methodologies to tackle the task, together with an explanation of Language Models and a taxonomy to easily distinguish them.

Chapter 3 delves into the methodological approach, starting from an overview of the Language Models employed for the task, it proceeds by delineating the framework developed and by explaining its main components, additionally it will define the empirical structure behind the experiments conducted.

Chapter 4 is dedicated to an objective presentation of the performances obtained with the different models and the various techniques utilized.

Chapter 5 embarks on a comprehensive discussion of the findings, it explores the theoretical and practical implications of the research, reflecting on how the advances in Language Models and methodological innovations contribute to the understanding and classification of citation intents. This section also addresses the challenges encountered during the research process, offering critical reflections on limitations and proposing avenues for future work. Additionally, this chapter connects the empirical results with existing literature, providing a comprehensive interpretation of how such findings align with or diverge from established theories and practices in the field.

Chapter 6 presents an application produced within the scope of this research. This section analyzes the architectural and structural components of this tool for both the backend and frontend parts.

Chapter 7 concludes this work, summarizing what is presented within the thesis together with a recall of the key findings. Finally, before concluding this dissertation, the section presents also future possibilities to enhance the understanding and the performances on CIC.

Chapter 2
An Overview of Citation Intent
Classification

2. An Overview of Citation Intent Classification

Within the field of Citation Intent Classification (CIC), significant advancements and developments have been produced in the last decade, mainly thanks to an increasing spectrum of available methodologies and theoretical frameworks. This chapter aims to offer a comprehensive overview of these varied approaches by providing some background knowledge of both conceptual theories and practical tools. Additionally, this section wants to highlight two, deeply linked, key challenges in this domain: the selection of a schema for the CIC task, and the scarcity of robust, reliable, and comprehensive datasets.

2.1. Defining a Feasible Citation Intent Classification Schema

It is extremely important to give enough consideration to the selection of a feasible classification schema for citation functions. In particular, practitioners should be aware that the chosen labels, as well as the number of classes they decide to include for the Citation Intent Classification task, have a fundamental role in both the overall utility and impact of a dataset (Pride, 2022) and in the results that can be obtained through automated methods. This is particularly true when it comes to the application of more advanced methodologies such as Language Models (LMs). LMs are extremely adaptable and capable of extracting and understaffing the context of portions of text - or sentences -, thus mapping to a meaningful and well-defined citation schema will for sure help the model in categorizing results in a more accurate manner.

This discourse traces its roots back to the seminal work “*Can Citation Indexing Be Automated?*”, by Garfield (1965). In this study, the author identifies 15 reasons for which an author may decide to cite another work, laying the foundations for further research in this domain. Following this foundational contribution many researchers have worked around the definition of a meaningful and accurate citation classification scheme (Kunnath et al., 2021b), enriching the understanding and application of such methodologies in scholarly research, and providing datasets to utilize for the CIC task.

To provide an example, Teufel and colleagues (2006b) presented a schema composed of twelve categories, and aimed at defining relational information between cited and citing entities. Such a schema may be functional in knowledge organization systems, but it is too scattered to be employed by the current classification tools. Some other schemes are the ones developed by Jurgens et al. (2016), Cohan et al. (2019), and Pride (2022), which will be detailed, together with the respective datasets, in Section 2 of this chapter. These schemes are more fine-grained with respect to the one developed by Teufel and colleagues, thus easier to employ for a classification task.

2.1.1. Classification Schema - Some Applications

Obtaining a good citation classification schema for annotating citations according to their purpose - or function - is extremely important for many possible applications. Among them, as stated also in the introduction of this work, citation analysis for research evaluation is a key operationalization of this kind of research (Swales, 1986; Teufel et al., 2006; Jochim and Schütze, 2012; Pride, 2022). This emphasis on a robust citation classification schema is rooted in the diverse functions citations serve in scholarly communication. These functions include but are not limited to, acknowledging the source of ideas, evidencing arguments, illustrating methodological similarities, and connecting related academic discussions. A well-designed schema can capture these facets, enabling more accurate analysis and interpretation of citation contexts.

In this, a central role is occupied by CiTO (Citation Typing Ontology), an ontology developed by Shotton (2010), and aimed at better describing the nature and role that citations may have. To do that, the author employs Semantic Web based technologies which enables the representation of citation data in a rich and structured format, allowing for an enhanced interoperability within the domain. This enriched interoperability derived by the use of Semantic Web formats such as RDF and OWL is the main reason why in this work the base categories defined within the used dataset have been mapped to object properties of the CiTO ontology before their operationalization, but this will be better explained in chapter 6.

Additionally, the importance of such a schema extends to numerous areas beyond research evaluation. To provide an example, in the domain of academic writing and literature reviews, understanding the intent behind citations can help in clarifying how each referenced work enriches the academic discourse, providing a more conscious way to engage with it. This insight, as stated also in the introduction of this dissertation, is particularly relevant in bibliometrics. Indeed, a better-defined classification can refine the precision of impact assessments and trend analyses, offering a deeper perspective on the influence and evolution of research, and providing instruments possibly useful to develop alternative and more *grounded* measures. An illustrative example of this last possible application is the study conducted by Jurgens et al. (2018) in “*Measuring the Evolution of a Scientific Field through Citation Frames*”, where the authors analyzed how scientific works frame their contributions through various types of citations, and the impact of this framing on the development of the field as a whole.

Overall, the creation of a detailed schema goes beyond technical accomplishment. It represents a core element in the advancement of scholarly communication, bridging the gap between quantitative citation metrics and qualitative academic impact. Such schema plays a pivotal role in shaping future research methodologies and analysis approaches within the scholarly domain, but also in the more general field of research assessment. This strategic development is thereby central to refine the understanding of academic influence in diverse domains (Pride, 2022).

2.2. The challenge of Datasets

A key aspect in developing an effective citation classification schema involves, as a sub-process, the development of a reliable, robust, and comprehensive dataset. The vast majority of the datasets designed for classifying citation contexts use their own specific and newly developed schema, thus making the integration of different datasets way more complicated. Such development of different and multifaceted citation schemes is indeed a good practice, mainly because it pushes for advancement in the field, but the problem arises when looking at the composition of such datasets.

Undoubtedly, providing the possibility to extend the various contributions could be important, primarily because this field faces a significant challenge due to the lack of extensive, highly curated, and diverse datasets (Cohan et al., 2019). This is mainly due to the resource-intensive work required to manually annotate them (Pride, 2022), and to the need of many different experts in many different fields capable - ideally trained - to fulfill this manual classification. Manual annotation is crucial to obtain a reliable starting point for developing accurate classifiers, and before this, it is way more crucial in developing reliable and useful datasets. Currently, despite the diversity of approaches and theoretical models explored in citation intent research, there exists a limited number of manually annotated datasets. These available datasets are inadequate to serve as a definitive Gold Standard for the field.

This section will briefly present the few trustworthy datasets that have been produced for the CIC task, starting from the first trusted benchmark. Subsequently, the section will dive deeper into the only dataset that could be considered sufficiently curated and populated to be defined as a good starting point: the SciCite Dataset, developed by Cohan et al. (2019). Finally, will be briefly presented the highly promising dataset built by D. Pride in his PhD Thesis (2022), which is not yet publicly available as of today.

2.2.1. ACL-ARC Dataset

The creation of the ACL-ARC Dataset (Jurgens et al., 2018) for Citation Intent Classification represents the first real useful contribution to the understanding of the facets of citation contexts within the specialized field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Computational Linguistics. Originating from the broader *ACL Anthology Reference Corpus*, developed by Bird et al. (2008), this dataset narrows its lens to a subset of conference and journal articles, providing a rich, though monodisciplinary, ground for examining citation intents.

Jurgens and colleagues (2018) extracted nearly 2000 citations from a randomly selected pool of papers contained in the reference anthology and manually annotated them thanks to the work of some experts in the NLP field⁴. The authors employed a six-label schema to categorize the intents - or functions - of citations, as shown in **Table 2**.

Even though the ACL-ARC dataset benefits from manual annotation by experts, it is very limited in both the number of citations it contains and in its disciplinary focus, further constraining its comprehensiveness. These limitations result in a dataset that is less than ideal, providing for classifiers that are likely domain-specific, as well as mostly unable to generalize to new citation contexts for the underrepresented classes, reflecting thus the limitations and the narrow scope of the dataset.

Citation Intent	Count
BACKGROUND	1021
USES	365
COMPARES OR CONTRASTS	344
MOTIVATION	98
CONTINUATION	73
FUTURE	68

Table 2. *ACL-ARC Dataset Citation Intents occurrences*

⁴ “The data was split into three standard stratified sets of train, validation, and test with 85% of data used for training and remaining 15% divided equally for validation and test. Each citation unit includes information about the immediate citation context, surrounding context, as well as information about the citing and cited paper.” (Cohan et al., 2019).

2.2.2. SciCite Dataset

The development of *SciCite* by Cohan and colleagues (2019) at the Allen Institute for Artificial Intelligence⁵ (*AllenAI*), marks a significant advancement in the field of Citation Intent Classification (CIC). Unlike the more narrowly focused ACL-ARC Dataset, SciCite covers a wider spectrum of academic disciplines, incorporating citations extracted from both computer science and medicine-related domains. This expansion into multiple domains significantly enhances the dataset's versatility and applicability, making it a more reliable and trustworthy benchmark for the CIC task.

All the citations contained within the SciCite Dataset have been manually annotated through the crowdsourcing platform *Figure Eight*⁶, after being harvested through *science-parse*⁷, a sophisticated tool for extracting scientific content, from a selection of papers sampled from the *Semantic Scholar Corpus*⁸. The authors of the dataset, in contrast to the detailed six-label schema used in the ACL-ARC Dataset, preferred a more coarse-grained approach to classification, providing a narrower and more broadly applicable outline. They supply three possible labels, applied to nearly 11000 citation contexts⁹, accompanied with additional metadata such as the title of the section in which the citation is contained, IDs of the publications, confidence levels, and so on. The labels, together with the count of datapoints, are presented in **Table 3**, which provides a comparison between ACL-ARC Dataset and SciCite. A brief and visual presentation of missing datapoints is provided in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Missing datapoints in SciCite.

⁵ <https://allenai.org/>

⁶ For additional information about the annotation procedure refer to the original article (Cohan et al., 2019). For more information on the figure-eight crowd source platform visit the following link: <https://www.figure-eight.com/platform/>.

⁷ It is a software developed by the same AllenAI Institute (<https://github.com/allenai/science-parse>).

⁸ It also provides an API for extracting additional data about these and other papers (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/>).

⁹ Also in this case, we have a predefined train-validation-test split, where the training set contains 8194 contexts, the validation 916, and finally the test set has 1859 datapoints. The information contained in this dataset, beside the context and the title of the section containing the citation, are basically general metadata about the beginning and the end of the citation, the confidence of the annotators for the label, and so on. These details, mainly for what concerns this particular dataset, will be presented with higher specificity in the experiment's related sections.

Dataset	Categories (distribution)	Source	#papers	#instances
ACL-ARC	Background (0.51) Extends (0.04) Uses (0.19) Motivation (0.05) Compare/Contrast (0.18) Future work (0.04)	Computational Linguistics	186	1,941
SciCite	Background (0.58) Method (0.29) Result comparison (0.13)	Computer Science & Medicine	6,627	11,020

Table 3. *SciCite and ACL-ARC Comparison.*
 Characteristics of SciCite compared with ACL-ARC dataset - From Cohan et al. (2019).

As reported in the introductory part of this overview, this dataset is the best choice at the moment even though it is not perfect. It presents both a quite large number of datapoints, as well as a relatively multidisciplinary provenience of citation contexts. It is the dataset used for the vast majority of benchmark experiments, and it is easily accessible in a Huggingface¹⁰ Dataset library-compliant form. The main drawback of this dataset is represented by its unbalanced composition. This is a problem for what concerns the use of machine learning-based approaches, with an underrepresentation of the *Result* class with respect to the other two (see **Figure 3**). Nevertheless, this dataset is the one used to carry out all the experiments described in this work.

Figure 3. *SciCite Datapoints Distribution.*
 Distribution of datapoints in the three classes covered by the SciCite Dataset.

¹⁰ <https://huggingface.co/>

2.2.3. ACT Dataset

Finally, even though this dataset has not been publicly released yet, it seems to be particularly relevant for the CIC domain. Pride, together with Harag and Knoth (2019), have developed the *ACT (Academic Citation Typing) Platform*, an online tool enabling the upload of a full-text research paper, which gives the possibility to rapidly annotate and classify in-text citations, according to both purpose - or intent, or function - and influence. Upon this tool, Pride and Knoth (2020) have developed a new - really - multidisciplinary dataset, which contains 11233 annotations manually produced by 883 authors. This dataset introduces these two new constituents, which make it - ideally - considerably better than both SciCite and ACL-ARC datasets. Even though it has not yet been publicly released, the fact that it has been annotated directly by authors, and the fact that it is truly multidisciplinary, put it one step aside from the others.

Class Label	Description
BACKGROUND	The cited paper provides relevant Background information or is part of the body of literature.
USES	The citing paper uses the methodology or tools created by the cited paper.
COMPARE_CONTRAST - similarities - differences - disagreement	The citing paper expresses similarities or differences to, or disagrees with, the cited paper.
MOTIVATION	The citing paper is directly motivated by the cited paper.
EXTENSION	The citing paper extends the methods, tools or data etc. of the cited paper.
FUTURE	The cited paper may be a potential avenue for future work.

Table 4. *Description of labels within ACT.*
Labels used in the ACT Dataset and their description.
Table taken from Pride et al. (2019).

The authors have decided on a six-intent schema presented in **Table 4**, building mainly upon previous works such as the one of Teufel et al. (2006), or the more recent works by Jurgens et al. (2018) and Valenzuela et al. (2015), but also gaining insights from CiTO, the ontology developed by David Shotton (2010; Peroni, Shotton 2012), which presents 107 possible reasons behind a citation.

This dataset will hopefully be the first true gold standard for the task of Citation Intent Classification whenever it will be publicly released. As for now, we can get a grasp of the dataset through two subsets of the bigger ACT, used for two 3C (Citation Context Classification) shared tasks (WOSP2020 and SDP2021). The subset used in SDP2021 has subsequently been released under the name of *ACT2* dataset in the work of Kunnath et al. (2022). *ACT2* is not yet considerably a gold standard, presenting some errors and repetitions, which is not clear if are intended for the 3C SDP2021 task, or present even in the bigger ACT Dataset.

2.3. Methodological approaches

The following section contains an overview of the different methodological approaches that shaped the field of Citation Intent Classification. The examination starts with rule-based methods, and progressively proceeds across the predominant methodologies employed in Citation Intent Classification, arriving at the most recent and innovative approaches to this task.

2.3.1. Rule-Based Systems & Rule Engines

Rule-based methods rely on predefined rules and heuristics, usually developed by experts, to classify citations based on specific patterns or keywords. Even though somewhat rigid, these methodological approaches have been instrumental in setting the stage for more dynamic classification systems, providing a structured way to process and interpret academic text. The first work in this direction is the one of Garzone and Mercer (2000), where the authors tried for the first time to apply an automated method for the task of Citation Intent Classification. Additional works have followed, such as the one of Nanba et al. (2000), where the aim was to better classify citation areas through cue sentences.

Figure 4. Rule Based Systems - Working Mechanics.

Visual representation of Rule Based Systems based processes. Image taken from *What is Rule-Engine?* Katiyar, R. (2019).

These systems demonstrated to have several limitations, mainly related to the need for experts capable of devising meaningful rules and cue words, or sentences. Additionally, the flexibility of these classifiers is limited to the cases analyzed by the crafters of rules, thus laying too much on the expertise of their creators (see **Figure 4**).

2.3.2. Machine Learning Systems

With traditional machine learning (ML) techniques, which laid the foundational groundwork for pattern recognition and predictive modeling, it has been possible to assist in a major step toward the development of more dynamic and flexible classification systems. The first work in this direction, within the CIC task, is the one proposed by Teufel et al. (2006), where the authors applied the K-Nearest Neighbors Algorithm (K-NN) on a twelve-label schema for citation functions. Many other works have followed in this direction, testing every ML algorithm, such as Random Forest (RF), Naive Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and so on.

Even though with ML approaches it is possible to obtain more dynamic and flexible tools to solve the Citation Intent Classification task, the need for human expertise is still strong, mainly for what concerns the requirement to manually determine the features to be used for model's training (Su et al., 2019). Finally, considerably important is the lack of well-devised datasets until 2018, thus making it difficult to produce a valuable comparison with other approaches. This is true both for rule-based and ML-based systems. A work in this direction has been produced as one of the outcomes of this master thesis and will be presented in the methodological sections.

2.3.3. Deep Learning Systems

However, the advent of deep learning (DL) marked a paradigm shift within the context of Citation Intent Classification too, in particular with the introduction of models capable of learning intricate patterns from vast amounts of unstructured data, reducing the need for human expertise in the field, and thus bypassing also the limitations of ML-based systems. Indeed, despite their sophistication, the principal reason behind the adoption of DL systems lies exactly in the possibility of automatic feature extraction, obviating the necessity for manually crafted heuristics (Kunnath et al., 2021b). However, this advancement simultaneously accentuates the need for larger datasets to train these models effectively, datasets that, as detailed before, are not so good as of today.

Besides that, neural network architectures, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), have played a critical role in the advancement of understanding sequential and spatial relationships within data. Their implementation significantly strengthened the models' ability to interpret contextual nuances in citation contexts. CNNs, with their ability to process spatial hierarchies in data, have shown effectiveness in analyzing also textual contents¹¹ and, on the other hand, RNNs. Nevertheless, RNNs suffer from some major drawbacks, such as the *Vanishing and Exploding Gradient* problems, that prevent the network from considering less recent information and thus learning long-term dependencies, as pointed out by Bengio and colleagues (1994), and strongly confirmed by Pascanu et al., (2013). Another well-known limitation to the use of RNNs for text sequences is their short-term memory, which reduces their capability of retaining information when processing long sequences (Shiri et al., 2023), thus hindering their ability to effectively pay attention to the various facets of the texts they are considering.

To overcome these issues, some more advanced variants have been developed (see **Figure 5**), like Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, initially developed by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997), and further improved with generative-based intuitions by Graves (2013). An additional step in deciphering sequences came from Bidirectional LSTMs (BiLSTMs), an LSTM-based model trained on both past and future elements of the sequence it is analyzing (see **Figure 6**). This bidirectional approach enhances the network's ability to understand complex sequences, as demonstrated also in COVID-19 (Aldhyani, T. H.; Alkahtani, H., 2021), and medical language modeling-related studies (Conegruta et al., 2016).

Figure 5. Visual Comparison Between RNN, LSTM, and GRU Units. RNN, LSTM, and GRU cells (units). Image taken from *A Brief Introduction to Recurrent Neural Networks*. Image taken from Dancker (2022).

¹¹ CNNs are mainly used for Image related tasks.

Figure 6. BiLSTM: Architecture and Working Mechanics.

The image shows the BiLSTM architecture used for the medical language modelling and entity recognition tasks by Cornegruta and colleagues (2016). Despite the different field of application, this image is interesting because shows a general process involving a BiLSTM architecture, depicting in a clear way how it handles bidirectional fluxes of information. Image taken from Cornegruta et al. (2016).

The last improved version of RNN that will be described in this paragraph is the one utilizing Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs), aimed at solving the short-term memory problem of Recurrent Networks and at the same time providing for a simpler structure with respect to LSTM units based networks (Shiri et al., 2023). The GRU unit, first introduced by Cho and colleagues (2014), encapsulates the *input* and *forget* gates of LSTM units, into a unique *update gate* which, together with a *reset gate* and the *unit memory*, compose this advanced version of a recurrent cell. Through these gates, the Gated Recurrent Unit can selectively update and utilize information from previous time steps, thus comprehending, capturing, and elaborating long-term dependencies in sequences (Dutta et al., 2019; Shiri et al., 2023). In empirical evaluations though, GRU-based RNNs are not always considered to

be better than LSTM-based RNNs, indeed in the study conducted by Chung and colleagues (2014), GRU units are found to be comparable with LSTM units in terms of performance. Another study, conducted on Bitcoin price prediction (Dutta et al., 2019), suggests instead that GRU is better than LSTM-based models, so it probably really depends on the application. The key concept is that both LSTM and GRU-based networks perform better than more traditional approaches, these advanced versions of RNNs have been instrumental in understanding long sequences, a key aspect in deciphering text, thus pushing further also the advancements in Citation Intent Classification tasks.

2.3.4. Transformers and Language Models (LMs)

The field of natural language processing (NLP) and artificial intelligence (AI) has undergone a significant transformation with the advent of Language Models (LMs), and in particular with Large Language Models (LLMs). These models, designed to understand, generate, and interact with human language, are grounded in the principles of deep learning and neural networks. Taking back the definition provided by Shanahan (2022), LMs can be defined as “*generative mathematical models of the statistical distribution of tokens in the vast public corpus of human-generated text, where the tokens in question include words, parts of words, or individual characters including punctuation marks*”. These models are trained on massive text-based datasets, and this enables them to learn linguistic patterns, grammar, and context, as well as being extremely good at the understanding of sequential text data. Thanks to this training process, LMs exhibit also incredible abilities in the understanding of natural language and in solving complex tasks - either via text generation or encoding capabilities (Zhao et al., 2023).

The groundbreaking discovery, that subsequently led to the development of LMs¹², was the introduction of the *Transformer* architecture by Vaswani and colleagues in their seminal paper "*Attention is All You Need*" (2017). Such architecture, which comprises an *encoder*, a *decoder*, and an *attention* mechanism - that substitutes the previously dominant recurrence -, allows for significant parallel processing of input data, thus enhancing the performances of transformer-based models with respect to recurrent networks.

¹² In the context of this thesis I will refer to LMs as an umbrella term to talk about Large Language Models (LLMs), Pre-Trained Language Models (PLMs), and Small Scale Language Models. For an accurate distinction between these terms, please refer to **Appendix B.1**.

Briefly diving deeper into the Transformer's architecture, it is possible to see that the underlying mechanism that drives these incredible capacities is nothing more than the *Attention* function. The Attention function, and in particular the *self-attention* of Transformer models allows them to process all parts of the input data in parallel. This approach facilitates the model to learn directly from the relationships between all parts of the input data, without the need to consider and focus on their position within the sequence (Vaswani et al., 2017; Lin et al., 2022).

As said before, the Transformer is composed of two main parts:

- **Encoder:** it takes the input data sequence $X = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ and transforms it into a sequence of continuous representations $Z = (z_1, \dots, z_n)$ that holds all the learned information of the input. The encoder consists of a stack of identical layers, each containing two main sub-components:
 - **Self-Attention Mechanism:** allows the model to weigh the importance of different parts of the input data with respect to each other;
 - **Position-wise Feed-Forward Networks:** a set of fully connected layers applied to each position separately and identically.
- **Decoder:** given Z , the decoder generates the output sequence $Y = (y_1, \dots, y_m)$ of symbols one element at a time. At each step, the model is auto-regressive and consumes the previously generated symbols as additional input when generating the next (Vaswani et al., 2017). Like the encoder, the decoder is composed of a stack of identical layers, but with an additional sub-component:
 - **Encoder-Decoder Attention:** Allows the decoder to focus on different parts of the encoder's output for each step in the output sequence, providing for the auto-regressive behavior.

Finally, *position encoding*-related pieces of information are added at the end of both the encoder and the decoder, this is because the Transformer architecture does not use recurrence, and thus cannot understand the position of the input elements within the sequence¹³ (see **Figure 7**).

¹³ A more detailed discussion on the Transformer architecture is outside of the scopes of the present work. For more details inspect the original work from Vaswani et al. (2017).

Figure 7. *Transformer Architecture.*

As can be seen all the elements described above are present in the image. Input data pass through the encoder, gets elaborated and an internal representation is produced. Such internal representation is then passed to the decoder which returns tokens probabilities. All the other elements, such as self-attention and positional encoding are depicted (from the original paper by Vaswani et al., 2019).

Two of the reasons behind the success of Transformer over Recurrence are its enhanced ability in learning long-range dependencies, and the reduced complexity of computations and time needed for training. Additionally, empirical results show significant performance improvements with respect to recurrence-based networks (Vaswani et al., 2017).

Building upon the Transformer architecture, some advanced language models have been developed. Two of the most interesting and pivotal in guiding and shaping successive research have been GPT (*Generative Pre-trained Transformer*) (Radford et al., 2018) and BERT (*Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers*) (Devlin et al., 2018), together with their derivatives. These LMs, pre-trained on immense corpora, have demonstrated extraordinary capabilities in understanding and generating human-like text. Their proficiency in grasping the subtleties of language and context has been instrumental in advancing fields related to Natural Language Processing, as well as Citation Intent Classification, enabling more detailed and accurate interpretations of academic discourse.

Post initial training, LMs often undergo *fine-tuning*, a process where they are further trained on specific data tailored to particular tasks, or domains. This additional training process enhances their performance in specialized applications. However, despite their advancements, LMs face challenges, such as biases in training data, ethical worries, and the computational resources required for their training and operationalization are particularly high.

The progression from traditional machine learning techniques to sophisticated LMs marks a significant step in the methodological landscape for tackling NLP tasks such as Citation Intent Classification. Each approach has its set of unique strengths and limitations and has contributed - or still contributes - to pave the way up to Language Models, which are the main methodological focus of this thesis.

2.4. Language Models (LMs) - A Taxonomy of Architectures

Given that all the conducted experiments that will be presented in the following chapter make use of Language Models (LMs), this final part of the section will commence with an exploration of the LM landscape, which aims to provide a foundational understanding of the main kind of architectures.

As detailed before, Language Models (LMs) have significantly advanced the capabilities and possibilities within the Natural Language Processing (NLP) field. Their diversity in design and functionality plays a crucial role in the possibilities upon which researchers can build different applications. The categorization that this section wants to highlight is really broad, but also instrumental to the task. Indeed, LMs can be categorized based on their architectural composition into *encoder-only*, *decoder-only*, and *encoder-decoder* models (see **Figure 8**). Each type presents unique characteristics and is better suited for specific tasks with respect to others within the field of NLP. Starting from the Encoder-only models, this part will inspect possibilities and difficulties in the use of different architectural configurations.

Figure 8. Taxonomy of Pre-Trained LMs (PLMs).

Black line represents information flow in bidirectional models, while gray line represents left-to-right information flow. Encoder models are trained with context-aware objectives. Decoder models are trained with autoregressive objectives. Encoder-decoder models combines the two, which use context-aware structures as encoders and left-to-right structures as decoders. Image and description from Cao et al. (2023).

2.4.1. Encoder-Only Models

Encoder-only models, which may be exemplified by BERT (*Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers*) (Devlin et al., 2018), represent a type of neural network architecture that consists only of an encoder part, without the corresponding decoder, and are designed to process input text and produce a fixed-size, and contextually-informed representation of input data. This kind of model is extremely good in tasks that require a deep understanding of the text because the input gets processed and encoded into a latent space. Once the embedding is produced, this can be used for various downstream tasks such as classification, entity recognition, sentiment analysis, or any other task that requires a deep understanding of contextual information (Zhang et al., 2024). The architecture of encoder-only models allows them to focus on each part of the input in a bidirectional way, while considering the entire context, leading to a profound understanding of the text (see **Figure 9.a**).

Key Components:

- **Bidirectional Contextual Understanding:** Unlike traditional unidirectional models, encoder-only models analyze text by considering both the preceding and following contexts, allowing thus for a more comprehensive understanding.
- **Self-Attention Mechanism:** This allows the model to weigh and focus on different parts of the input text, depending on its relevance to the task at hand.

2.4.2. Decoder-Only Models

Decoder-only models, with GPT (*Generative Pre-trained Transformer*) (Radford et al., 2018) being a prime example, are mainly used for tasks involving the generation of sequences, or other forms of output data. Indeed, these models are good at producing coherent and contextually relevant outputs based on the input data (e.g. in a text-only model, the user provides a prompt and the model produces a relevant output), and unlike encoder-only models, which create a compact representation of the input data, decoder-only models focus on generating or expanding information (Cao et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024). They are particularly effective in applications such as language generation, creative writing, and continuation of text (see **Figure 9.b**).

Key Components:

- **Unidirectional Processing:** Decoder-only models process data in a forward direction, which is ideal for generating outputs that logically follow from a given input.
- **Generative Capabilities:** They excel at creating text that is coherent, logical, and contextually appropriate.

2.4.3. Encoder-Decoder Models

Encoder-decoder models, like T5 (*Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer*) (Raffel et al., 2019) and BART (*Bidirectional and Auto-Regressive Transformers*) (Lewis et al., 2019), combine the functionalities of both encoder and decoder architectures (see **Figure 9.c**). These models are highly versatile and can handle a wide range of tasks, from translation to summarization and question answering, and excel in tasks involving sequence-to-sequence transformations (Cao et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024).

Key Components:

- **Dual Architecture:** The encoder processes the input text and creates a contextual representation, which the decoder then uses to generate the output sequence.
- **Flexibility in Task Handling:** Their design allows them to be adept at both understanding and generating text, making them suitable for a wide array of NLP tasks¹⁴.

Figure 9. Common Architectures of LMs.

The image (taken from Zhang et al., 2024) depicts common architectures of LMs, such as (a) encoder-only, (b) decoder-only, and (c) encoder-decoder.

¹⁴ Additionally, a particular case is T5, which proposes a transformation of all the tasks in sequence-to-sequence format, resulting in an extremely flexible model.

Chapter 3

Methodology and Experiments

3. Methodology and Experiments

Building upon the diverse methodologies discussed in the previous chapter for the Citation Intent Classification (CIC) task, this section is dedicated to the theoretical explanation of the framework developed, as well as of the experiments carried out to generate the final research output of this work. The chapter will start with a presentation of the Language Models used to test the research question, then the focus will shift into the practical and experimental facets of this research. The second part of the chapter will provide a detailed presentation of the experimental framework, the implementation process, and the methods employed to ensure the validity and reliability of the results. Finally, this investigation will also dive deep into the specific configurations and adaptations of the LMs used.

3.1. Citation Intent Classification: promising LMs

Within Citation Intent Classification tasks, an array of diverse Pretrained Language Models (PLMs) can be deployed to obtain at least good outcomes. The delineation of PLMs into encoder-only, decoder-only, and encoder-decoder models provides valuable insights into their respective utilities in determinate contexts and under specific assumptions. For the CIC task, which is a classification problem, encoder-only models seem to be particularly advantaged. This preference is derived from the design of their architecture, which is particularly suited for processing and understanding textual data to generate contextualized representations of the input.

Furthermore, the specific linguistic content of scientific publications needs careful consideration because of the particular - and for sure not trivial - vocabulary on which it is constructed, characterized by a unique lexicon that is distinct from everyday conversational language. More than a specialized terminology, scientific discourse presents also a particular syntactical structure that is intrinsic to academic writing. Taking into consideration this distinction in vocabulary and sentence construction is crucial for the CIC task, as the efficacy of a LM in interpreting and classifying text is heavily influenced by its training data and, thus by its familiarity with the relevant linguistic domain.

Starting from this assumption, when applying LMs to Citation Intent Classification it is particularly important to ensure that the chosen model is not only specific in its architectural design but that it is also fine-tuned - or pre-trained - on a corpus that mirrors the specific language of academic discourse. Such specificity in training should theoretically enable the model to classify in a more precise way the intentions of the authors behind citations in scientific documents.

Seen these needs, and saw the fact that this research follows an exploratory approach trying to balance the experiments conducted within this work in between a various range of different models to draw broader insights on general possibilities to apply different kinds of processes to the CIC task, this work is built upon three language models. The factors taken into consideration for the choice of models are:

- **Architecture:** Theoretically, this investigation should prefer LMs with Encoder-only, or Encoder-Decoder, architectures for the reasons previously explained. But, since the main aim of this work is to inspect a wide spectrum of possibilities, also different architectures have been considered. In particular, one of the models presents an encoder-only setup, another one a decoder-only setup¹⁵, and an Autoregressive Language Model¹⁶.
- **Vocabulary:** The choice has also been guided by the particular vocabulary used by the various models. LMs trained on scientific-based corpora have been preferred if available.

Thus, the models used for the experiments behind this work are *SciBERT* (Beltagy et al., 2019), *Galactica* (Taylor et al., 2022), and *XLNet* (Yang et al., 2019). The latter is the only one that has not been trained mainly on a scientific-based corpora, but it is part of this work because of its impressive ability to understand language contexts, and mainly because an XLNet variation is the current State-Of-The-Art (SOTA) in CIC task on SciCite.

¹⁵ It is interesting to notice how this will perform on CIC task.

¹⁶ A kind of statistical or machine learning model known as an Autoregressive (AR) model makes predictions about the subsequent value in a series by analyzing the elements that came before it. These models offer predictions based on the supposition that the future values of the sequence are reliant, and build upon previous values. Autoregressive models are frequently used in natural language processing to create text or make predictions based on the prior words of a sentence. These models create coherent and contextually appropriate text by first learning the statistical patterns and relationships present in the training data.

3.1.1. SciBERT - The Scientific Evolution of BERT

SciBERT (Beltagy et al., 2019) emerges in the domain of language models (LMs) mainly because it is tailored specifically for processing and understanding scientific text. This model is a derivative of the well-known BERT (*Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers*) model (Devlin et al., 2018), and it basically inherits the foundational architecture and training process from it but diverges significantly in its training regime and intended application. Retaining the core architectural principles of BERT, SciBERT is also an encoder-only model famous for its deep bidirectional understanding of language. According to the general principles delineated in the previous chapter, the encoder-only structure of SciBERT enables the model to generate rich and contextually informed representations of the input text, making it particularly suitable for tasks requiring a particularly good understanding of complex - and, in this specific case, scientific - language, such as entity recognition, classification, and relation extraction.

The fundamental distinctiveness of SciBERT lies in its specialized vocabulary, SCIVOCAB, as named by Beltagy and colleagues (2019). Indeed, differently from BERT, which is trained on a general corpus, SciBERT is trained on a large corpus of scientific literature. This corpus encompasses a wide range of scientific fields, providing SciBERT with an extensive and specific vocabulary, as well as with an enhanced ability to comprehend the structure of scientific language, both these elements are useful for a better understanding of the scientific discourse with respect to a more general model. Indeed, this specific training allows SciBERT to perform extremely well on texts presenting scientific terminology and concepts, a domain where general language models might have lower performances.

SciBERT has been used in the field of Citation Intent Classification, mainly by Cohan et al. (2019), and also in a newly developed prompt-based framework (Lahiri et al., 2023), which makes use of the OpenPrompt library (Ding et al., 2021), SciBERT, and a verbalizer specifically developed for the task. Both experiments with SciBERT yield the same interesting results.

3.1.2. Galactica - A Large Language Model for Science

Galactica (Taylor et al., 2022) is a groundbreaking language model, designed explicitly for understanding and generating scientific content, and one of the most impressive abilities of this LM is its capability to generate meaningful and well-structured citations. This model represents an innovative step in the realm of Large Language Models (LLMs), specifically developed in response to the demands of the scientific community for models capable of dealing with scientific literature and data.

Galactica, similarly to other advanced LLMs, is built upon a sophisticated neural network architecture in a decoder-only setup. As briefly introduced, this model is mainly optimized for dealing with the complexities of scientific texts from a wide perspective, including the ability to process not only textual data but also scientific formulas, diagrams, and data tables, which in general are the main components of scholarly articles. Indeed, a defining feature of Galactica, which is also the main reason for the presence of the model within the context of this work, is its extensive training on a diverse array of scientific materials. This includes academic papers, textbooks, lecture notes, and other scholarly publications across various scientific fields. With the assimilation of such a vast body of academic knowledge, Galactica is a perfect fit for all the tasks that require an in-depth understanding of scientific concepts, structure, terminology, and methodologies. Even though its capabilities would be better framed within a task that implies text generation, summarization, literature review, or even new hypotheses generation, it is interesting to test the capabilities of Galactica models in a classification task that deeply involves academic language.

Galactica finds its application in a wide spectrum of scientific endeavors. It can assist researchers in exploring vast literature databases or in suggesting comprehensive literature reviews, and it can be applied also as a tool for educational purposes, helping in the creation of scientific summaries or explanations for students. At the moment, it has not yet been tested on the Citation Intent Classification task, but the possibilities are intriguing, in particular for what concerns in-context learning, which is unfortunately outside the scope of this work.

3.1.3. XLNet - An innovative Language Modeling objective

XLNet (Yang et al., 2019) is a significant innovation in the field of LMs, in particular, its training offers an innovative approach to natural language processing. As an extension and refinement of transformer-based models, XLNet draws from the Transformer-XL model developed by Dan and colleagues (2019), and addresses certain limitations of its predecessors, like BERT (Devlin et al., 2018), while bringing a new perspective to language modeling.

This model, despite being presenting an Encoder-only architecture, is distinguished by a unique training strategy, which combines some of the main aspects of both Autoregressive (AR)¹⁷ and Autoencoding (AE) models (Minaee et al., 2024). In particular, with the AR pretraining objective, a model tries to estimate the probability distribution of a text corpus (Yang et al., 2019), starting from the assumption that the next token in a sequence is directly dependent on the previous tokens. Thus, AR models try to learn statistical patterns within the training sentences, aiming at maximizing the probability of the subsequent word by computing the density estimation of the sequence. A major drawback is that the model, given a text sequence $X = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$, factorizes the likelihood into *either* a forward product (**Eq. 1.a**) or a backward product (**Eq. 1.b**) (Peters et al., 2018), thus it is only trained to encode a unidirectional context. This limitation is particularly relevant when it comes to tasks that need a deep bidirectional context understanding (Yang et al., 2019).

$$a) p(X) = \prod_{t=1}^T p(x_t | X_{<t}) \qquad b) p(X) = \prod_{t=T}^1 p(x_t | X_{>t})$$

Eq. 1. Likelihood of (a) a forward product and (b) a backward product. Basically these two equations define the product of joint probabilities, derived from the *chain rule*. With $X_{<t} = (x_1, \dots, x_T)$ denoting the vector of words in position t in ascending order, and $X_{>t}$ basically denoting the opposite order (also visible from the product indexing).

Subsequently, when it comes to surpassing the limitations from which AE models suffer, must be considered the following factors:

¹⁷ The term has its roots in the literature on time-series, in which the observations from the previous time-steps are used to predict the value at the current time step.

- **Pretraining and fine-tuning discrepancy:** AE models like BERT use a masked language model (MLM) approach¹⁸ during pretraining (Devlin et al., 2018), where some of the tokens are masked, and the model learns to predict them based on the context provided by the unmasked tokens. However, this masking process does not occur during fine-tuning or inference, leading to a discrepancy between pretraining and application scenarios. This discrepancy can impact the model's performance since it must adapt to a slightly different task than it was originally trained on.
- **Independence assumption:** In the MLM task, each masked token is predicted independently of the other masked tokens, but just according to the unmasked context. This approach simplifies the complex dependencies between words in natural language, potentially limiting the model's ability to capture intricate relationships and long-term dependencies.

With the *permutation-based language modeling* objective of XLNet, the problem related to the use of a single stream during context understanding is surpassed (Minaee et al., 2024). This happens because this language modeling computes the density estimation of each possible permutation of input tokens, thus XLNet grasps a generalized understanding of language, capturing both the syntactic and semantic relationships between tokens, so each position learns to utilize contextual information from all positions, bypassing in this way the absence of bidirectional estimations in AR models. Additionally, since it computes the joint probability of each possible permutation of input tokens - it is an AR model -, it does not rely on data corruption (Yang et al., 2019), thus it doesn't require [MASK] tokens, overcoming also both the independence assumption and the discrepancy between AEs use and pretraining, finally providing for an unsupervised learning context.

By integrating the strengths of AR and AE, XLNet achieves a more comprehensive understanding of language when compared to traditional masked language models. However, this complexity also means that XLNet requires high computational resources for training and fine-tuning, which can be a limitation for some applications. Despite that, an XLNet-based model, ImpactCite (Mercier et al., 2020), is the current state-of-the-art (SOTA) for the Citation Intent Classification task on the SciCite dataset.

¹⁸ Masked Language Modeling (MLM) is a training technique in NLP. In MLM, a certain percentage of the input tokens are randomly masked during the training process. The model is then asked to predict these masked tokens based solely on their context. For instance, in a sentence like "The cat sat on the [MASK]," the model must predict the masked word (e.g., "mat") using the surrounding words as context.

3.2. Experimental framework

Building upon the foundational concepts presented in the previous chapters and sections, this study has employed three distinct Language Models for inspecting and analyzing their performances within the Citation Intent Classification (CIC) task. These models, each exemplifying a unique facet of natural language processing capabilities and data processing, have been selected to align with the specific requirements and objectives of this dissertation. Each model's unique attributes and strengths contribute to a multi-faceted approach to language processing, ensuring a thorough and nuanced analysis within the scope of this work.

Concerning the experiments conducted on the SciCite dataset, this research makes use of *SciBERT* (cased/uncased versions), *Galactica* (125M-mini version), and *XLNet* (base-cased version) as baseline models, within a general and consistent (in testing and training conditions) framework developed to harmonize different experiments within the CIC domain. The experimental framework incorporates a novel and highly detailed fine-tuning strategy, which implements a *Population Based Training* (PBT) scheduler to explore the hyperparameter space effectively and dynamically during the main fine-tuning phase, together with some particular care with respect to resource consumption and training times.

Besides this first part of the framework, which involves experiments within the general scope of fine-tuning, the second part of this chapter explores the development of some *Ensemble Models*, to explore various possibilities to enhance the results that can be obtained within the Citation Intent Classification task¹⁹. Additionally, another objective of this research is to test basic assumptions such as the one of Liu and colleagues (2022), and Mohammed and Kora (2023) - and many others -, who state that ensemble learning techniques, by combining multiple weak classifier models, are capable of obtaining a better and more comprehensive strong model, in particular in situations in which class imbalance and underrepresentation of some classes, which may cause some kind of performance degradation of the classifier (Salunkhe and Mali, 2016), is a primary concern. On top of these base models, some meta-classifiers will encompass a diverse array of strategies, including, as a baseline performance comparison, a majority voting system²⁰. By employing this method, the

¹⁹ The base models used for the ensemble construction are the ones in their original configuration, thus not the fine-tuned models.

²⁰ This strategy involves aggregating the decisions of the individual classifiers and adopting the most common outcome as the final decision.

framework aims to mitigate individual model biases and errors, trying to enhance the robustness of the classification process. This multi-layered approach is designed to leverage the strengths of each model and classifier, trying to optimize the results that can be obtained within the CIC task with SciCite.

In summary, this section will provide a detailed description of the methodological approaches adopted for the exploration and evaluation of the selected Language Models. It will detail the fine-tuning process, the development of binary classifiers, and the integration of these components into a meta-classification framework. This chapter is thus divided into two main sections: the first will elucidate the fine-tuning process for a classifier aimed at recognizing the correct label, and the second will instead detail how the ensemble-based approach has been carried out, providing insights on the binary fine-tuning strategy and the various possibilities analyzed for the construction of the meta-classifier on top of the three binary models. This approach is expected to yield valuable insights into the comparative strengths and weaknesses of the models in the context of Citation Intent Classification.

3.2.1. Enhancing Large Language Models through Population-Based fine-tuning

This first section of the methodological exploration part will delve into an in-depth analysis and explanation of the advanced fine-tuning strategy adopted for the CIC task, detailing the integration with a Population Based Training (PBT) scheduler (see **Figure 10**), with fine-grained evaluations, and mixed precision training techniques. This detailed overview aims to explain the intuitions behind the possible synergistic interplay between a sophisticated and optimized fine-tuning technique and the dynamic and adaptive nature of PBT, together with some strategies to avoid overfitting and to lower the number of resources needed to train these large models, aiming to demonstrate how this integration increases the performances and efficacy of the selected Language Models (LMs), while also reducing memory consumption and resources usage.

The core of the section is in the integration of these complex methodologies, showing how the combination of these various techniques provides for a more robust and efficient fine-tuning process for the LMs considered. The discussion will also dive deep into the practicalities of the implementation of this integrated strategy, highlighting both the challenges encountered and the solutions devised to overcome them.

3.2.1.1. Fine-tuning strategy

The fine-tuning strategy presented in this work, as briefly introduced above, offers an innovative approach to the performance optimization of the selected language models. This integrated strategy offers a different perspective on LM fine-tuning, also providing for a more automated process, where the influence of the researcher is strongly reduced.

The first element that needs to be considered within the framework of this strategy is the use of mixed precision training, employing PyTorch's *autocast* and *GradScaler* modules. Mixed precision allows for a more efficient allocation of computational resources by utilizing both 16-bit and 32-bit floating-point operations. By employing this strategy, the training process significantly accelerates, while maintaining the model's accuracy and performance. This approach is particularly beneficial in dealing with large models and datasets, as it reduces the memory footprint and allows for faster and equally precise computations, which are crucial for handling tasks like Citation Intent Classification (or other general classification tasks in the field of NLP) with models composed of a huge amount of parameters. Furthermore, together with the mixed precision training strategy, such a loop also involves a fine-grained evaluation process²¹, which has been considered in particular as a possible solution to overcome the overfitting problem of which these LMs usually suffer²².

Basically, given the susceptibility to overfitting inherent in fine-tuning LLMs, due to their extensive number of parameters, the fine-grained evaluation strategy has been adopted for model validation and selection. In particular, to mitigate such risk within the training process, each model, upon validation, is saved independently, overwriting less performing models, thus facilitating the subsequent retrieval of the best model with respect to the performance metric. The criterion for the selection of the optimal model from the entire fine-tuning process is singularly focused on the performance metric of validation loss. The intuition behind the use of validation loss as performance metric derives from the will to obtain a model which is the best possible model for its generalization capabilities. The reliance on validation loss as a performance metric ensures that the chosen model provides for robust performances on unseen data, thereby enhancing the validity and applicability of the model in practical scenarios.

²¹ During every fine-tuning epoch, each model is evaluated multiple times and the best performing ones are stored in memory to be reused for PBT, but also in order to be reloaded if at some point it incurs in overfitting.

²² During the discovery process, many experiments have been carried out before the development of this framework, and each of the models that have been employed was highly prone to overfitting in standard conditions, reaching their maximum performance peak around the second fine-tuning epoch.

A core element initially devised for the fine-tuning strategy employed in this research was the integration of a *Weighted Cross-Entropy Loss* function to evaluate the performances of such models. This adaptation of the conventional *Cross-Entropy Loss* has been specifically formulated to help within contexts of class imbalances - present, as yet said, also in the SciCite dataset - by computing weight tensors with respect to the number of datapoints of each class. The initial intuition of computing and integrating class-specific weights into the loss function was guided by the expectation to enhance the models' ability to equally represent each class, thereby resulting in a more balanced and impartial classification outcome (refer to **Appendix A.1** for details). Extensive experimental evaluations have been conducted to compare the effectiveness of the weighted loss function against its unweighted counterpart. These tests have been crucial in determining the actual impact of implementing the weighted loss on model performance, mainly because the empirical findings revealed that the incorporation of the weighted loss does not yield any kind of significant improvement in models' performance. As a result of these findings, the option to utilize a weighted loss has been finally excluded from the fine-tuning strategy²³ to reduce the complexity within the HP search space. This brief examination highlights the importance of empirical validations and testing scenarios in the optimization of machine learning models, ensuring that each component of the model training process effectively contributes positively to the overall performance. Despite that, within the developed framework, the option to integrate a weighted loss is still present, giving room for additional experimentations in different scenarios (*CIC Framework*, Paolini, 2024).

An additional element that has been extensively investigated within this research is the optimization of custom tokenization and data preprocessing steps, to enhance the model's understanding of citation contexts. The augmentation of data with additional contextual information provides the models with a more comprehensive view of the citation's purpose and meaning, thereby enhancing the results of the classification. Mainly, this augmentation process has been carried out by adding some structural placeholders inside each sentence. These additional data are meant to give some kind of structural continuity to sentences, providing for a model capable of better recognizing where both the title of the section containing the citation, as well as the citation context itself are located within the sentence.

²³ The same is not true for the fine-tuning of the binary classifiers, which will be detailed in the following section.

The standardized prompt used for the pure fine-tuning step is the following:

```
'[SECTION]: '+section_title+'. [CITATION]: '+citation_context+'. It has function: '
```

Furthermore, each model then has its specific requirements and set of features needed for the tokenization and fine-tuning processes²⁴, which have been taken into consideration.

Finally, this strategy includes meticulous management of the training and validation process, utilizing both a learning rate (lr) scheduling technique and an early stopping mechanism. These integrations are critical in preventing overfitting and ensuring that the models are trained to their highest potential. For what concerns these two strategies, the lr Scheduling has been set with **patience=6**, **factor=0.75**, **min_lr=8e-7**, and **cooldown=2**; instead, the early stopping strategy has been set to have **patience=8**.

Figure 10. Population Based Training: Exploitation and Exploration Dynamics. A visual explanation of the dynamics that guide Population Based Training (Jaderberg et al., 2017)

²⁴ For example, Galactica tokenizers do not have a padding token, which has been added manually. Or, again, Galactica models do not need `token_type_ids`, which are instead needed by SciBERT and XLNet based models. Or, finally, SciBERT based models have the first three layers freezer, to avoid overfitting.

3.2.1.2. Population Based Training configuration

As has been briefly introduced in the opening of this section, a Population Based Training (PBT) scheduler (see **Figure 10**) was integrated into the framework. To do that, the Ray Train²⁵ and Ray Tune²⁶ libraries have been employed, in order to improve the fine-tuning process of the models and navigate the hyperparameters' search space efficiently and dynamically. The adopted approach to PBT in this series of experiments mainly adheres to the detailed methodology outlined in the original implementation of PBT (Jaderberg et al., 2017) (detailed in **Appendix A.2**), while it incorporates also certain modifications that differentiate it from the standard protocol.

The main deviation in PBT implementation is the integration of a fine-grained evaluation mechanism. This enhancement has been designed to provide more comprehensive insights into the model's performance during the training process and to obtain final models that are at their best possible state of generalization capacities on unseen data. To integrate this refined evaluation approach, the frequency of checkpointing has been increased with respect to standard implementations. Such checkpoints mainly serve as critical junctures in the training process, allowing for the assessment and adjustment of model parameters, as well as for the generalization capabilities assessment. Furthermore, the dynamics of *exploitation* and *exploration* - the processes of selecting the best-performing models and perturbing their hyperparameters to explore new configurations - within the PBT framework (described in **Appendix A.2**) have been specifically configured to be performed after every *eight* evaluation cycles - checkpointing steps. This interval has been carefully chosen after various empirical evaluations, the intuition behind this empirical research is the will to find a perfect balance between the need for sufficient data accumulation for informed decision-making, against the desire for meaningfully timed adjustments of the models' training trajectories²⁷. Another reason for this high interval is the risk of overfitting or catastrophic forgetting that could affect LMs when updating HP like *lr* too frequently. Diving deeper into the implementation of such interval, must be noticed that every evaluation step is performed after every 30 batch passes with a batch size of 32, or after every 60 batch passes when the batch size is 16. This difference builds upon the intuition for which it is not useful to evaluate and compare two

²⁵ <https://docs.ray.io/en/latest/train/train.html>

²⁶ <https://docs.ray.io/en/latest/tune/index.html>

²⁷ Indeed, in particular when it comes to LMs, changing HPs during training may lead to a high risk of training instability, producing thus a "confused" model, unable to efficiently understand textual contexts.

models after x training batches if the amount of data seen by the models is different at such time step. For a more detailed understanding inspect *CIC Framework* (Paolini, 2024).

Finally, the rationale behind these modifications is the will to strike an optimal balance between the thoroughness of the model evaluations, and the agility of the adaptive training process. By doing so, the implementation aims at pushing the PBT scheduler capacity to dynamically refine models in response to the ongoing performance feedbacks, thus enhancing the overall efficacy of the fine-tuning process.

3.2.1.3. Hyperparameter Search Space

The configuration space for the PBT is defined with several key hyperparameters, each playing a critical role in the training and optimization of the models:

- **Number of Epochs:** Set to a fixed value of **5**, providing a consistent time frame for model training across different configurations, even though this interval is for sure stopped around the third epoch, even because a stopping condition criterion that ends training after a bit more than 3 epochs has been added in the PBT scheduler. This is motivated by the faster convergence of these models, when accompanied by PBT, with respect to traditional settings.
- **Batch Size:** A grid search approach was utilized, focusing on batch sizes of **16** and **32**. To ensure a balanced comparison²⁸ during the exploitation phase of the training, a novel adjustment strategy was implemented. This strategy involves treating models trained with a batch size of 16 as equivalent to half the step count of those trained with a batch size of 32. This adjustment is crucial for *preventing a bias* towards models with larger batch sizes, thereby maintaining *fairness* in the evaluation and selection process.
- **Seed:** A single seed value (**1482**) has been used, even though the research by Dodge et al. (2020) suggests searching for different seeds, for different tasks, in particular when fine-tuning pre-trained language models (PLMs). The conclusions of the work by Dodge and colleagues (2020) are rooted in the empirical findings according to which seed values influence weight initialization and data order, which in turn result in higher or lower performances for the fine-tuned models.

²⁸ By default, the exploitation process favors the most performing models, and clearly a model (batch size 32) that at the same time-step has seen twice the number of datapoints of another model with half the batch size of the first (16) will be preferred because will probably have obtained better performances.

The reason this search has been avoided is based on the fact that PBT yet requires high time and resources, adding additional HP to search - besides the main ones - would have led to really high training times. Still, the consistent application of the same seed here ensures reproducibility²⁹ and stability in training outcomes.

- **Learning Rate (*lr*):** The learning rate is set to uniformly sample between **1e-5** and **2e-5**, adjusting the recommendations for similar fine-tuning tasks (Sun et al., 2020), within the context of this framework. This range is critical for optimizing the rate at which the model learns, trying to avoid both rapid divergence and slow convergence.
- **Weight Decay:** The search space for weight decay is defined as a uniform distribution between **0.02** and **0.01**, recognizing its potentially significant impact on the final results. This HP, in particular when it comes to LMs fine-tuning, is extremely influential, it adds a penalty to the magnitude of the weights of the loss function. It is a form of regularization that penalizes large weights, and its primary purpose is to reduce overfitting by preventing the weights from growing too large.
- **Token Maximum Length:** Two values, **256** and **312**, are grid-searched to determine the optimal input token length for the model, trying to balance between adequate context and computational efficiency.
- **Loss Function:** The loss function is set to a non-weighted version, following the experimental findings that do not demonstrate a significant improvement with weighted loss in this particular scenario.
- **Optimizer:** **AdamW** is the chosen optimizer. The optimizer works on two different groups of parameters in two different ways. In particular, it considers the optimization of all the model's parameters with a weight decay, except for what concerns *bias* and *LayerNormalization*³⁰. The exclusion of the weights of the *LayerNormalization* from the optimization with weight decay is because these parameters are part of a normalization mechanism rather than direct factors in representing the input-output relationship in the same way as traditional weights. Applying weight decay to these parameters may interfere with the normalization process, potentially leading to the

²⁹ Even though complete reproducibility is not guaranteed by default in PyTorch (<https://pytorch.org/docs/stable/notes/randomness.html>), and even less with PBT and continuous search spaces, results remain more or less consistent across various experiments.

³⁰ The parameters pertaining to Normalization and Bias are not necessarily present in each LLM, it really depends from the authors. For example, none of the various Galactica models uses any bias, this is an architectural choice derived from the work of Chowdhery et al. (2022), in which the authors discovered that avoiding the use of biases in dense kernels and layer norms provide for a higher training stability, especially for large models.

destabilization of the training dynamics. Instead, for what concerns the *bias* terms, applying weight decay to them can lead to suboptimal training. Mainly because these do not interact with the input data in the same multiplicative way as weights. Weight decay penalization, in the case of *bias* terms is generally unnecessary and can harm the model's ability to fit the data. Empirically, it has been observed that the exclusion of *bias* terms and *LayerNorm* weights from weight decay contributes to achieving more stable and effective training of neural networks (Ba et al., 2016; Loshchilov and Hutter, 2017; Li et al., 2018; Lahiri et al. 2023).

3.2.1.4. PBT Configuration and Scheduler

The PBT scheduler is configured with several parameters to control the training and optimization process:

- **Evaluation Interval:** Models are evaluated every **30** batches³¹, which determines the frequency of model performance assessment and checkpointing.
- **Perturbation Interval:** Set to eight times the evaluation interval, indicating the frequency at which hyperparameter perturbation occurs.
- **Quantile Fraction and Resample Probability:** These settings control the selection of top-performing models and the probability of resampling new configurations, respectively. The values are, respectively, **0.5** and **0.3**.
- **Hyperparameter Mutations:** Specifies the range for mutating the learning rate and weight decay during the PBT process, allowing for exploration beyond the initial search space. The values chosen for these ranges are, respectively a uniform distribution from which to sample between **9e-6** and **3e-5**, and another uniform distribution between **0.001** and **0.03**.

³¹ 60 in case of batch size of 16.

3.2.1.5. Resource Allocation and Execution

The training process leverages Ray's capabilities for distributed computing. Each trial is allocated 3 (or 4, depending on model size) CPU cores and 25% (or 30%, depending on model size) of a GPU³², enabling parallel training of multiple models. This setup, while potentially slowing individual model performance, enhances overall experimentation throughput. The tuning process is encapsulated within Ray's Tuner interface, with configurations for run-stopping criteria, checkpoint management, and storage paths. The experiment is configured to run for slightly more than 800 training iterations (a bit more than 3 epochs), providing a comprehensive scope for model training and optimization.

3.2.1.6. Concluding Remarks on PBT Integration

In summary, this section has presented a detailed account of the hyperparameter search space and the PBT configuration employed for the fine-tuning of the chosen LMs. The strategic choices made in the HP selection, combined with the sophisticated setup of the PBT scheduler and resource allocation, exemplify a meticulously curated approach to optimizing model performance. The integration of these elements within the PBT framework highlights the commitment to achieving a fine balance between exploration and exploitation in the hyperparameter space, finally aiming to enhance the performances and the efficiency of the general fine-tuning process (see pseudocode in **Figure 11**).

³² All the experiments make use of Google Colab A100 GPU, for a reference: <https://colab.research.google.com/notebooks/pro.ipynb>

Algorithm 1 Adaptive Fine-Tuning with PBT and Mixed Precision

Input: Dataset D , Tokenization T , Model Checkpoint M , Hyperparameters C , Evaluation Interval E , Stopping Criteria S

Output: Optimally Tuned Model M^* , Optimal Hyperparameters H^*

```
1:
2: Initialize Ray and PBT with configuration space  $C$ 
3: for each configuration  $h \in C$  do
4:   Load and tokenize dataset  $D$  with  $T$ 
5:   Initialize model  $M$  from checkpoint  $M$  with  $h$ , enable mixed precision
6:   Freeze initial layers of  $M$  for pre-trained knowledge retention ▷ If needed
7:   Define optimizer  $O$  and scheduler  $LRS$  based on  $h$ 
8:   Prepare data loaders for  $D$ 
9:    $L_{\text{best}} \leftarrow \infty$  ▷ Initialize best validation loss tracking
10:  Initialize mixed precision scaling for enhanced training efficiency
11:  while not max epochs or  $S$  do
12:    for each batch  $b$  in training loader do
13:      Apply mixed precision training to forward and backward passes
14:      Update  $M$  using  $O$ , adjust using mixed precision scaling
15:      if batch index mod  $E == 0$  then
16:        Evaluate  $M$  for  $L_{\text{val}}$  and  $F1_{\text{val}}$ , apply scaling correction
17:        if  $L_{\text{val}} < L_{\text{best}}$  then
18:           $L_{\text{best}} = L_{\text{val}}$ , update  $M^*$ ,  $H^*$ , checkpoint  $M$ 
19:        end if
20:        Perform exploitation and exploration in PBT:
21:          Exploit by copying parameters from top performers to underperformers
22:          Explore by perturbing the hyperparameters of underperformers
23:        end if
24:        if no improvement for  $S$ , restore from last checkpoint then
25:          break ▷ Enables early stopping and continuation from checkpoint
26:        end if
27:      end for
28:    end while
29:  end for
30: return Optimally tuned model  $M^*$  and hyperparameters  $H^*$ 
```

Figure 11. Pseudocode: Adaptive Fine-Tuning Strategy.

This pseudocode outlines the adaptive fine-tuning process for the Language Models used in the framework, using Population Based Training (PBT) combined with mixed precision training techniques. The algorithm initiates by setting up the training environment with a specified configuration space that includes hyperparameters for optimization. Key inputs include the dataset, tokenization specifics, an initial model checkpoint, and parameters defining the evaluation interval and stopping criteria. It concludes by returning the optimally tuned model and its corresponding hyperparameters.

The process exemplifies the sophisticated approach to fine-tuning described in detail above, incorporating techniques such as mixed precision and PBT. Through this adaptive methodology, the algorithm seeks to achieve high levels of model performance and generalization, leveraging both the computational efficiency of mixed precision training and the dynamic hyperparameter tuning capabilities of PBT.

3.2.2. Harnessing the Power of Ensemble Strategies for Enhanced Citation Intent Classification

This second section aims to comprehensively delineate the other part of this framework, this will detail the ensemble strategy, based on the development of three base binary language model classifiers. Each of these, derived from the fine-tuning of the reference LM, is dedicated to a specific class. Each binary classifier aims to understand and discern whether a given citation can be classified within the class it is trained on or not, thus operating within a binary classification context for each class. This will result in the production of a *Background-based model*, a *Method-based model*, and a *Result-based model*. Additionally, this section will also encompass a series of experimental analyses aimed at identifying the most effective meta-classifier to be used as head over the three base models.

Firstly, the evaluations will encompass a high-score voting mechanism, where the decision of the most confident model is taken as the correct classification. This approach is based on the assumption that the model with the highest confidence in its discerning is most likely to be accurate (Mohammed and Kora, 2023). Secondly, this experimentation explores a variety of machine learning algorithms, each of which is designed with a grid search for hyperparameter optimization, and cross-validation. This exploration includes an array of algorithms such as Random Forest (RF) (Breiman, L., 2001; Louppe, G., 2014), XGBoost (Chen and Guestrin, 2016), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) (Cunningham and Delany, 2021), and Support Vector Machine (SVM) (Hearst et al., 1998). The goal here is to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of these diverse algorithms in the context of meta-classification. In addition to these traditional machine learning approaches, this section will also present Deep Learning experiments, in particular involving two types of neural networks: a *Feed Forward Neural Network* (Sazli, M., 2006) and a *One-Dimension Convolutional Neural Network* (1D-CNN) (Alzubaidi et al., 2021). These neural network models offer a different paradigm for meta-classification and will be assessed for their suitability and performance in this specific task, additionally, this comparison could also bring interesting insights with respect to traditional ML approaches when compared to DL Neural Networks.

3.2.2.1. Binary Fine-tuning strategy

The first relevant element of this second part, being also a pre-requisite for the following steps, is represented by the transformation of the original labels of the SciCite dataset (Method, Background, and Result) to fit a binary classification framework. This preprocessing step is central to converting and rearranging the multi-class classification problem into a series of binary classification tasks, thereby producing the ground base for the fine-tuning of the reference Language Model with respect to each specific citation intent - or function. Such a preprocessing step is simply aimed at converting the labels of the original SciCite Dataset (0, 1, 2) into either 0 (to represent a negative match) or 1 (positive match).

The fine-tuning process employs the AdamW optimizer with **weight_decay=0.01** for all the layers - besides normalization and bias, as extensively explained in the previous section -, and a learning rate scheduler (LRS): **ReduceLRonPlateau**, designed with **patience=6**, a decrease factor of **0.2** and **8** cooldown steps after each reduction. This LRS is used to adjust the learning rate according to improvements in validation loss. The loss used is, again, the *Cross-Entropy Loss*³³, but this time in its weighted version³⁴. The loop includes mixed precision training using PyTorch's *autocast* and *GradScaler* for efficient computation. The initial learning rate is fixed at **2e-5**.

Also within this binary context, a fine-grained evaluation during the training loop has been implemented, thus the model is trained and evaluated at specified intervals, and more than once during each epoch. This setup not only facilitates frequent assessment of model performance but also enables the saving of the model state when it achieves the lowest validation loss w.r.t. preceding values. Additionally, as before, also in this case the frequent evaluations allow to avoid overfitting by overwriting less performing models, thus conserving the state of the best model w.r.t. generalization performances. Early stopping is also incorporated to stop training if no improvement in validation loss is observed over a predefined number of steps (**patience=50**), enhancing computational efficiency.

³³ In this loop it is used the binary version. For a reference see **Appendix A.1**.

³⁴ Here the weighted loss produces improvements in the performances, this is due to the higher imbalance between class representation within the binary task.

This approach to LMs’ fine-tuning for binary classification tasks within the Citation Intent Classification task is thus characterized by an initial label transformation, a rigorous and curated training and evaluation process, and an efficient utilization of computational resources (pseudocode can be found in **Figure 12**).

Binary base models: Preprocessing steps & Training

Algorithm 1 Data Preprocessing for Binary Base Models

Require: Raw dataset D , Tokenizer T

Ensure: Tokenized and split dataset: D_{train} , D_{val} , Class weights W_{class}

- 1: Tokenize D using tokenizer T to produce tokenized dataset $D_{tokenized}$.
 - 2: **for** each label type $\in \{\text{Background, Method, Result}\}$ **do**
 - 3: Transform $D_{tokenized}$ labels for the specific task.
 - 4: Compute class weights W_{class} based on the new label distribution.
 - 5: Split $D_{tokenized}$ into training D_{train} and validation D_{val} sets.
 - 6: **end for**
-

Algorithm 2 Binary Base Model Fine-Tuning with Mixed Precision

Require: D_{train} , D_{val} , Class weights W_{class} , Pre-trained mLanguage Model M

Ensure: Fine-tuned models: $M_{Background}$, M_{Method} , M_{Result}

- 1: **for** each model $\in \{\text{Background, Method, Result}\}$ **do**
 - 2: Load pre-trained model checkpoint into M .
 - 3: Initialize CrossEntropyLoss with W_{class} .
 - 4: Use AdamW as optimizer O with learning rate $\eta = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ and weight decay $\lambda = 0.01$.
 - 5: Configure ReduceLROnPlateau scheduler S with patience and factor settings.
 - 6: Enable GradScaler G for mixed precision training.
 - 7: **for** $epoch = 1$ to E **do**
 - 8: **for** each batch (X_{batch}, y_{batch}) in D_{train} **do**
 - 9: Forward pass with autocast: $P_{batch} = M(X_{batch})$.
 - 10: Compute loss $L_{batch} = L(P_{batch}, y_{batch})$.
 - 11: Backward pass and update M using O with scaled gradients by G .
 - 12: **end for**
 - 13: Evaluate M on D_{val} , compute validation loss L_{val} .
 - 14: Adjust O learning rate based on L_{val} using S .
 - 15: **if** L_{val} improves **then**
 - 16: Save current state of M as the best model.
 - 17: **end if**
 - 18: **end for**
 - 19: **end for**
-

Figure 12. Pseudocode: Fine-Tuning of Base Binary Models

Pseudocode describing the preprocessing steps and the training loop for the fine tuning process of the three base classifiers (LMs). This is generalizable to all the experiments, but for a more detailed analysis of each refer to *CIC Framework* (Paolini, 2024).

3.2.2.2. Meta-Classifiers: Introduction and Max Score Voting System

Once the three binary baseline Language Models have been correctly fine-tuned to fit the binary classification task, to employ the fixed probability scores generated by these baseline models some kind of strategy - or system - must be used to obtain the final classification and bring back the problem to a multi-class classification task. With this aim, there are two main possibilities: the first involves the use of a voting system, while the second integrates and trains a meta-classifier on top of the baseline predictions (Mohammed and Kora, 2023). Both strategies have been implemented in this research. These meta-classifiers are designed to recognize patterns within the predictions of the baseline models, thereby aiding in the determination of the most plausible classification for each citation instance. The intuition is that even though two - or three - models recognize the same sentence to be of their own class with high confidence, the meta-classifier may be capable of understanding the weakness and strengths of these binary classifiers, thus mapping an approximation function based *directly* on confidence scores, without the need to backpropagate results down to the baseline models. In this way, it is possible to obtain more efficient and faster training, without the consumption of additional computational resources. This section, together with the following ones, is aimed to outline the various meta-classifiers implemented, together with design principles and strategic optimization of their hyperparameters, highlighting their roles in the overall classification process.

Among the various strategies employed, the Max-Score classification system (Mohammed and Kora, 2023) stands out for its simplicity and effectiveness, and it is employed as a baseline for performance improvements. This system operates on the premise of selecting the class label corresponding to the highest probability score from the predictions made by the baseline models. The approach involves analyzing the probability scores associated with each class for a given citation, as predicted by the three base LMs. The class with the highest probability score is chosen as the final classification for that citation. This decision is based on the assumption that the model with the highest confidence in its prediction is most likely to be accurate (Mohammed and Kora, 2023). Utilizing such a system as a baseline is also useful to understand whether the intuition on confidence approximation is well-grounded: if this non-back-propagated strategy turns out to be effectively beneficial, leading to the conclusion that particular patterns - outside of the confidence-

based selection - arise, then it is possible to further improve the strategy, and draw new insights on how LMs works³⁵.

Thereby, in contrast with the established baseline, a range of strategies has been explored to identify the most effective meta-classifier for the task at hand. These approaches have been broadly categorized into two distinct groups: those based on traditional Machine Learning (ML) techniques (see **Figure 13** for pseudocode reference) and those leveraging deep learning (DL) methodologies (see **Figure 14** for pseudocode reference). The subsequent sections will provide a detailed account of these strategies, elucidating the nuances and specificities of each approach within the context of meta-classification.

3.2.2.3. Meta-Classifiers: Machine Learning-based approaches

Random Forest Classifier (RF)

The Random Forest Classifier is a robust and versatile machine learning algorithm, usually used for classification tasks. It operates by building multiple decision trees during training and returning as output the class that is the mode of the classes (classification) of the individual trees (Breiman, L., 2001; Louppe, G., 2014). This ensemble approach enhances the predictive accuracy and controls overfitting, making it a popular choice in various applications.

In the conducted experiment, a comprehensive grid search was employed to optimize the hyperparameters of the Random Forest Classifier, together with a cross-validation (5)³⁶. This search aimed to identify the best combination of parameters that maximizes the Macro-F1 score (thus, generalization capabilities across the three classes), the reference metric for evaluating performance in the intent classification task. The specific hyperparameters explored include:

- **n_estimators**: Number of trees in the forest.
 - *Values*: [10, 50, 100]
 - *Impact*: Increasing the number of trees can enhance the model's accuracy but may also increase computational complexity and time needed for training and classification.

³⁵ To this aim, additional studies should be performed. In particular comparative strategies within the ensemble domain would shed light to such nuances.

³⁶ The training and validation datasets were combined (stacked) to form a comprehensive set for the cross validation process. This applies to all the models presented in ML related sections from now on.

- **max_depth**: Maximum depth of the trees.
 - *Values*: [3, 5]
 - *Impact*: Deeper trees can capture more complex patterns, but might lead to overfitting. Shallower trees may prevent overfitting but could underfit the data, thus approximating the base function in a non-effective manner.
- **min_samples_split**: Minimum number of samples required to split an internal node.
 - *Values*: [2, 5]
 - *Impact*: Higher values prevent the creation of nodes that do not have sufficient data to meaningfully discern, ideally reducing overfitting.
- **min_samples_leaf**: Minimum number of samples required to be at a leaf node.
 - *Values*: [3, 5]
 - *Impact*: Setting this value higher can smooth the model - mainly this is useful for regression problems, but may benefit from it also a classification task.
- **bootstrap**: Whether bootstrap samples are used when building trees.
 - *Values*: [True, False]
 - *Impact*: Bootstrap sampling introduces randomness into the model, this helps to improve the accuracy of the model by reducing its variance.
- **criterion**: The function to measure the quality of a split.
 - *Values*: ['gini', 'entropy']
 - *Impact*: Different criteria can lead to different performance and tree structures.
- **class_weight**: Weights associated with classes.
 - *Values*: ['balanced', None]
 - *Impact*: Balancing class weights is critical in datasets with imbalanced classes to ensure fair representation in decision-making, as extensively explained.

Using the **GridSearchCV** method from *Scikit-learn*, the Random Forest Classifier was subjected to a grid search with cross-validation (5). A seed has been set for reproducibility, and the search has been focused on optimizing the Macro-F1 score to balance the precision and recall across all classes.

Upon completion of the grid search, the best combination of hyperparameters and the corresponding best score (Macro-F1 score) are extracted. This process ensures a meticulous and data-driven approach to determining the most effective Random Forest model configuration for the meta-classification task in Citation Intent Classification.

XGBoost Classifier

XGBoost (eXtreme Gradient Boosting) is a highly efficient and scalable implementation of the gradient boosting framework, renowned for its performance and speed (Chen and Guestrin, 2016). XGBoost has gained popularity in a wide range of classification tasks due to its ability to handle sparse data and its robustness against overfitting. It operates by sequentially adding predictors to an ensemble, each one correcting its predecessor, thus improving the model's predictive abilities.

In this experiment, a cross-validation (5), together with a grid search, have been employed to fine-tune the hyperparameters of the XGBoost Classifier, aiming to the enhancement of its performance in terms of the Macro-F1 score. The selected hyperparameters for the grid search include:

- **learning_rate**: Determines the step size at each iteration while moving toward a minimum of a loss function (hopefully global).
 - *Values*: [0.001, 0.01, 0.05]
 - *Impact*: A smaller learning rate requires more boosting rounds but often improves model performance and generalization capacities.
- **max_depth**: Maximum depth of a tree.
 - *Values*: [3, 5, 10]
 - *Impact*: Controls the depth of the tree. Deeper trees can model more complex patterns but might lead to overfitting.
- **n_estimators**: Number of boosting rounds.
 - *Values*: [10, 50, 100]
 - *Impact*: More rounds can lead to a better fit, but too many might lead to overfitting.

- **gamma**: Minimum loss reduction required to make a further partition on a leaf node of the tree (also known as *regularization parameter*).
 - *Values*: [0, 0.05, 0.1]
 - *Impact*: Higher values make the algorithm conservative, preventing overfitting but might lead it to underfit if too high.

Utilizing **GridSearchCV**, the XGBoost model underwent a grid search process for HP optimization with cross-validation, aiming at the improvement of the Macro-F1 score. The evaluation metric was set to **mlogloss** to minimize log-loss in multi-class classification, and a fixed random state ensured reproducibility. Upon completion, the grid search yielded the best combination of hyperparameters, alongside the best Macro-F1 score achieved.

K-Nearest Neighbors Classifier (K-NN)

The K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN) Classifier is a fundamental machine learning algorithm based on the principle of proximity, thus classifies instances based on the majority class among its nearest neighbors in the feature space (Cunningham and Delany, 2007; Cunningham and Delany, 2020). K-NN is inherently simple but also powerful, making it suitable for a variety of classification tasks. Its deterministic nature (i.e., the lack of randomness in its process) ensures consistent results under the same conditions.

In this experiment, together with cross-validation (5), a grid search was designed to determine the optimal number of neighbors (**n_neighbors**) for the K-NN Classifier. This hyperparameter is critical in K-NN, as it directly influences the classification decision. The search involved:

- **n_neighbors**: Number of neighbors to use for k-neighbors queries.
 - *Values*: **Range from 1 to 100.**
 - *Impact*: A smaller number of neighbors can make the model sensitive to noise in the data (overfitting), while a larger number provides a more generalized result but might smooth out important distinctions (underfitting).

Again, a **GridSearchCV** object was instantiated to conduct the grid search over the defined range of **n_neighbors**, to optimize the Macro-F1 score. The K-NN model, without any randomness in the process - due to its deterministic nature - was subjected to this search across the specified *k* ranges.

At the end of the process, the grid search provided detailed results, including scores for different parameter combinations, and the best-performing model in terms of the Macro-F1 score has been identified, and its corresponding optimal number of neighbors reported. By systematically exploring a wide range of values, this experiment aimed to strike the number that best balances the trade-off between sensitivity to noise and generalization ability.

Support Vector Machine (SVM)

The Support Vector Machine (SVM) Classifier is a powerful and versatile supervised machine learning algorithm, usually very effectively used for both classification and regression tasks. Known for its effectiveness in high-dimensional spaces and its versatility in handling various types of data, SVM operates on the principle of finding the hyperplane that best separates different classes in the feature space (Hearst et al., 1998) - this is true for classification problems, for regression the mechanism is slightly different.

In this experiment, together with cross-validation (5), a grid search was conducted to fine-tune the hyperparameters of the SVM Classifier. The focus was - again - on the optimization of the Macro-F1 score. The hyperparameters explored in the grid search include:

- **c** (*Regularization Parameter*):
 - *Values*: [0.01, 0.1]
 - *Impact*: Controls the trade-off between achieving a low training error and a low testing error (i.e., the model's complexity and generalization capability). A higher value of C might lead to overfitting.

- **Gamma** (Kernel Coefficient for **rbf**, **poly**, and **sigmoid**):
 - *Values*: [1, 'scale', 'auto']
 - *Impact*: Determines the influence of individual training samples; higher values lead to tighter and bumpier decision boundaries.

- **Kernel**:
 - *Values*: ['rbf', 'sigmoid']
 - *Impact*: Specifies the kernel type to be used in the algorithm. The radial Basis Function (*rbf*) and Sigmoid kernels are chosen for their different approaches in handling non-linear data.

- **Class Weight:**
 - *Values:* [None, 'balanced']
 - *Impact:* Offers a way to handle class imbalance by assigning weights inversely proportional to class frequencies, or not.

Using the **GridSearchCV** method, the SVM model was subjected to a comprehensive grid search process. The SVM classifier was configured to produce probability estimates and a fixed random state was set for reproducibility.

MetaClassifier heads: Machine Learning based

Algorithm 1 Machine Learning Meta-Classifiers Training

Require: Stacked features: F_{train} , F_{val} , F_{test} , and their labels

Ensure: Evaluated models: SVM, RandomForest, XGBoost, KNN with performance metrics

- 1: Define hyperparameter grids for tuning:
 - SVM
 - RandomForest
 - XGBoost
 - KNN
 - 2: **for** each classifier type $\in \{\text{SVM, RandomForest, XGBoost, KNN}\}$ **do**
 - 3: Perform grid search with cross-validation on F_{train} to find optimal hyperparameters.
 - 4: Train the classifier on F_{train} using the best set of hyperparameters.
 - 5: Evaluate the classifier on F_{test} .
 - 6: Compute accuracy and F1 score.
 - 7: Report metrics.
 - 8: **end for**
-

Figure 13. *Pseudocode: Training of Machine Learning Metaclassifiers*

The pseudocode reports (a general overview of) the training process of each meta-classifier head based on pure Machine Learning algorithms. The precise steps, together with Hyperparameter search spaces have been defined in this section. Detailed process can be found in *CIC Framework* (Paolini, 2024).

3.2.2.4. Meta-Classifiers: Deep Learning based approaches

Feed Forward Neural Network (FFNN)

The FeedForward Neural Network (FFNN) presented here has a multi-layer architecture designed for the meta-classification task in the Citation Intent Classification problem. This network is structured to process input data through multiple linear layers and normalization steps, coupled with non-linear activation functions and dropout for regularization. It is composed of the following key elements:

- **Linear Layers** (Fully Connected Layers): The network consists of five linear layers, with the first layer taking an input of size **6** and subsequently expanding and contracting the feature space across layers. The final layer outputs a vector of size **3**, corresponding to the class probabilities.
- **Batch Normalization**: each linear layer is followed by a **Batch Normalization layer**. Batch Normalization is employed to stabilize and speed up the training by normalizing the inputs to each layer. It helps in reducing internal covariate shifts and can also have a slight regularization effect.
- **Activation Functions**: The network uses **GELU** (*Gaussian Error Linear Units*) and **SELU** (*Scaled Exponential Linear Units*) as activation functions after the first four linear layers. **GELU** is used for the first two layers and **SELU** for the next two layers. These activation functions introduce non-linearity into the network, enabling it to learn more complex patterns in the data.
- **Dropout**: Dropout with a rate of **0.5** is applied after each batch normalization step. This is a regularization technique to prevent overfitting by randomly setting a fraction of input units to reduce to 0 during training.
- **Output Layer and Softmax Activation**: The final linear layer outputs the *logits* for the three classes. A **softmax** function is applied to these logits to obtain probabilities for each class. The **softmax** function is crucial for multi-class classification tasks as it converts the logits into probabilities that sum to one.

This FeedForward Neural Network architecture is designed to capture complex relationships in the data while mitigating the risk of overfitting. The network's design has been devised to balance model complexity and generalization capability.

1-D Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN)

The 1D Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN) developed for this task makes use of PyTorch's *nn.Module* and it is structured to process input data through convolutional layers, batch normalization, dropout, and fully connected layers. The architecture comprises several layers and components, essential for capturing and understanding hierarchies in the input data:

- **Convolutional Layers:** The network includes two 1D-convolutional layers (*Conv1D*), where the first layer expands the input channel from **1** to **16**, and the second layer further expands it to **32** channels. The kernel size of **3** is used in both layers. These layers are key elements in the extraction of local and spatial features from within the input data.
- **Batch Normalization:** Each convolutional layer is followed by a batch normalization layer.
- **Dropout:** Dropout layers with a dropout rate of **0.5** are applied after batch normalization.
- **Fully Connected (FC) Layers:** After the convolutional layers, the network includes two fully connected layers. The first FC layer reduces the dimension from the flattened convolutional layer outputs to **64**, and the second FC layer outputs the final classification logits for three classes. These layers are instrumental in integrating the learned features for classification.

The *forward method* defines the data flow through the network. The input data is first unsqueezed to add an extra dimension, making it compatible with the 1D convolutional layers. The data then sequentially passes through the convolutional layers, with **GELU** activation, batch normalization, and dropout applied. After the second convolutional layer, the data is flattened again and passed through the fully connected layers. A **SELU** activation function is used after the first FC layer. The final output is obtained by applying a **softmax** function to the output of the second FC layer, yielding a probability distribution over the classes. This 1D-CNN architecture is designed to efficiently process and classify data by leveraging convolutional layers for feature extraction and fully connected layers for classification.

MetaClassifier heads: Deep Learning based

Algorithm 1 Training Preparation for DL Meta-Classifiers

Require: Meta-features F_{train} , F_{val} , F_{test} ; Class weights W_{class}

Ensure: Data loaders for F_{train} , F_{val} ; Configured loss function and optimizer

- 1: Prepare data loaders for F_{train} and F_{val} with batch size 128.
 - 2: Initialize CrossEntropyLoss with W_{class} for handling class imbalance.
 - 3: Select AdamW optimizer with learning rate $\eta = 1e - 5$ and weight decay $\lambda = 1e - 2$.
 - 4: Configure GradScaler for mixed precision training.
-

Algorithm 2 Training Loop Execution for FFNN and 1D CNN Meta-Classifiers

Require: Data loaders for F_{train} and F_{val} ; Models: FFNN, 1D CNN; Loss function; Optimizer; GradScaler

Ensure: Trained Models: FFNN, 1D CNN

- 1: **for** each model $\in \{\text{FFNN}, \text{1D CNN}\}$ **do**
 - 2: **for** each epoch up to E **do**
 - 3: **for** each batch (X_{batch}, y_{batch}) in F_{train} **do**
 - 4: Perform forward pass with autocast for mixed precision.
 - 5: Compute loss and backpropagate errors.
 - 6: Update model weights using the optimizer.
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: Validate model on F_{val} , compute metrics.
 - 9: Implement early stopping based on validation metrics improvement.
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: **end for**
-

Algorithm 3 Evaluation of Trained FFNN and 1D CNN Meta-Classifiers

Require: Best performing FFNN, 1D CNN; Test data loader F_{test}

Ensure: Performance metrics: Accuracy, F1 score for FFNN, 1D CNN

- 1: **for** each model $\in \{\text{FFNN}, \text{1D CNN}\}$ **do**
 - 2: Evaluate the model on F_{test} to compute accuracy and F1 score.
 - 3: Report the performance metrics.
 - 4: **end for**
-

Figure 14. *Pseudocode: Training and Evaluation of Deep Learning Metaclassifiers*

The pseudocode reports the training process, together with preparation and evaluation, of each meta-classifier head based on Deep Learning Neural Networks (NN) - namely the FFNN and the 1D-CNN. The precise steps, together with the specifics of the two NN have been defined in this section. Detailed architectures and processing steps can be found in *CIC Framework* (Paolini, 2024).

3.2.2.5. Concluding Remarks on the Ensemble Strategy

The ensemble-based strategy developed in this research and described inters section represents an innovative approach to tackle the Citation Intent Classification task from a different perspective, leveraging the strengths of various models and techniques, which will be extensively detailed in the following chapter.

In conclusion, this strategy (**Figure 15**) demonstrates a robust and non-resource-intensive approach to the Citation Intent Classification task. By combining the predictive power of fine-tuned LMs with the various capabilities of meta-classifier heads, this strategy presents an innovative approach to the CIC task, potentially helping in a better understanding of Language Models functioning, for which additional studies are required. The careful tuning and integration of these models underscore the potential of ensemble methods in tackling complex classification challenges, paving the way for future advancements in the field of Citation Intent Classification.

Figure 15. *Ensemble Strategy overview.*
A diagram explaining the steps within the Ensemble Strategy.

Chapter 4

Results

4. Results

This section outlines the outcomes derived from the series of experiments performed as part of this study (see **Table 5**) on the SciCite dataset. These results are focused on *Macro-F1* and *Accuracy* scores, where Macro-F1 is a metric that balances precision and recall across all classes equally, while accuracy measures the overall correctness of predictions, making Macro-F1 more suitable for imbalanced datasets, such as SciCite. The presentation follows the same organizational structure used for the description of the framework in Chapter 3, ensuring ease of understanding. For a full understanding and a detailed inspection of the final configurations of the models you should refer to the *CIC Framework* (Paolini, 2024), where also results and additional visualizations are reported.

4.1. SciBERT based models

In the following paragraphs are detailed the findings related to SciBERT-based models (see **Figure 16** for the uncased version, **Figure 17** for the cased version, and **Figure 18** for a comparison between the two versions). This description of the performances and efficacy of models grounded in the SciBERT architecture provides critical insights into their applicability and utility within the scope of this research objectives. Such insights will be detailed in the following chapter.

4.1.1. Fine-Tuning with Population Based Training (PBT) - SciBERT

Uncased Base Model

The SciBERT Uncased model, fine-tuned through Population Based Training, reached an optimized setup with a batch size of **16**, a learning rate of approximately **2.03e-05**, and a weight decay of **0.02788**, with tokens processed up with a maximum length of **312**. This configuration led to a test loss of 0.3218, achieving an overall test Macro-F1 score of 87.06%, with category-specific F1 scores of 89.76% for Method, 89.61% for Background, and 81.80% for Result. The test accuracy stood at 88.54%. The model can be inspected and tested in *FTCIC_SciBERT_Uncased* (Paolini, 2024).

Figure 16. *SciBERT (Uncased) Based Models: Performance Comparison.*

The plots above show a comparison between the performances of all the experiments conducted utilizing *SciBERT Uncased* as base model. The first (right) presents accuracy related results, while the second (left) details the Macro-F1 scores obtained by these models.

Cased Base Model

Through Population Based Training, the SciBERT Cased model was fine-tuned to an optimal configuration that included a batch size of **16**, a learning rate of approximately **2.13e-05**, and a weight decay of **0.01546**, processing tokens up to a maximum length of **312**. The evaluation of this model configuration on the test set yielded a loss of 0.3748, a Macro-F1 score of 87.00%, and an accuracy of 88.27%. The detailed F1 scores for the Method, Background, and Result categories were 88.68%, 89.54%, and 82.78% respectively.

The model can be inspected and tested in *FTCIC_SciBERT_Cased* (Paolini, 2024).

4.1.2. Ensemble Models Performance - SciBERT

In this section are reported the results of SciBERT-based models, fine-tuned on the binary classification task. The three base models, together with the best meta-classifier can be found as *EnsCIC_SciBERT_Uncased* (Paolini, 2024), relative to the uncased versions of the fine-tuned binary models, and as *EnsCIC_SciBERT_Cased* (Paolini, 2024) for the cased version.

4.1.2.1. Max Score Voting - SciBERT

Uncased Base model

Using a max score voting mechanism among the three ensemble base models, the baseline reached an accuracy of 88.54% and a Macro-F1-score of 87.35%, with the Method, Background, and Result categories achieving F1 scores of 89%, 90%, and 84%, respectively.

Cased Base model

Implementing the highest score voting among the ensemble models resulted in an accuracy of 88.33% and a Macro-F1-score of 86.65%, with the Method, Background, and Result categories attaining F1 scores of 91%, 89%, and 80%, respectively.

Figure 17. *SciBERT (Cased) Based Models: Performance Comparison.*

The plots above show a comparison between the performances of all the experiments conducted utilizing *SciBERT Cased* as base model. The first presents accuracy related results, while the second details the Macro-F1 scores obtained by these models.

4.1.2.2. Random Forest - SciBERT

Uncased Base model

The Random Forest classifier, following a specific parameter set including '**bootstrap**': **False** and '**criterion**': '**entropy**', among others³⁷, recorded an accuracy of 88.17% and a Macro-F1 score of 86.85%. The F1 scores for the Method, Background, and Result categories were 89%, 89%, and 82%, respectively.

Cased Base model

The Random Forest classifier, optimized with parameters such as '**bootstrap**': **True** and '**n_estimators**': **50**, achieved an accuracy of 88.70% and a Macro-F1-score of 87.09%. The F1 scores for the Method, Background, and Result were 90%, 90%, and 81%, respectively.

4.1.2.3. XGBoost - SciBERT

Uncased Base model

The best configuration, with '**gamma**': **0**, '**learning_rate**': **0.001**, '**max_depth**': **3**, and '**n_estimators**': **10**, led the XGBoost model to achieve an accuracy of 89.08% and a Macro-F1-score of 87.77%. F1 scores for individual categories were 89% for Method, 90% for Background, and 83% for Result.

Cased Base model

The XGBoost metaclassifier model, configured with '**gamma**':**0.05**, '**learning_rate**':**0.05**, and '**n_estimators**': **50**, reported an accuracy of 88.54% and a Macro-F1-score of 86.91%. F1 scores across the categories were 91% for Method, 90% for Background, and 80% for Result.

³⁷ Please, to see the full configuration when it is not reported, refer to *CIC Framework* (Paolini, 2024).

4.1.2.4. K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN) - SciBERT

Uncased Base model

The K-NN model, optimized with **37 neighbors**, showed an accuracy of 88.60% and a Macro-F1-score of 87.33%. The F1 scores across categories were consistent, with the method, background, and result categories each achieving scores around 89%, 90%, and 83%, respectively.

Cased Base model

Optimized with **72 neighbors**, the K-NN model demonstrated an accuracy of 88.86% and a Macro-F1 score of 87.31%. The model achieved F1 scores of 91% for Method, 90% for Background, and 81% for Result.

4.1.2.5. Support Vector Machine (SVM) - SciBERT

Uncased Base model

The Support Vector Machine fine-tuned to a configuration of **C=0.01**, **class weight balanced**, **gamma** set to '**scale**', and utilizing the '**rbf**' **kernel**, demonstrated an accuracy of 88.33% alongside a Macro-F1-score of 87.12%. The model's F1 scores for Method, Background, and Result classifications were observed at 89%, 89%, and 83%, respectively, indicating the model's balanced performance across different citation intents.

Cased Base model

The SVM fine-tuned to a configuration of **C=0.1** and '**gamma**' set to '**auto**', exhibited an accuracy of 88.43% and a Macro-F1-score of 86.81%. The F1 scores were consistent across categories at 90% for both Method and Background and 81% for Result.

4.1.2.6. Feed Forward Neural Network - SciBERT

Uncased Base model

The Feed Forward Neural Network was evaluated, revealing a test loss of 0.6585, a Macro-F1 score of 87.85%, and an accuracy of 88.97%. The model exhibited F1 scores of 89.38% for method, 90.06% for background, and 84.09% for result, showcasing its effectiveness in accurately classifying citations across all categories.

Cased Base model

This model recorded a test loss of 0.6525, a Macro-F1 score of 88.41%, and an impressive accuracy of 89.73%. The detailed F1 scores were notably high, with Method at 90.18%, Background at 90.99%, and Result at 84.07%.

4.1.2.7. 1D Convolutional Neural Network - SciBERT

Uncased Base model

Testing of the 1D Convolutional Neural Network yielded a test loss of 0.6585, closely mirroring the performance of the feedforward network. The Macro-F1 score achieved was 87.66%, with an accuracy rate of 88.81%. The category-specific F1 scores were 88.83% for method, 90.06% for background, and 84.07% for result, further affirming the model's competent classification capabilities.

Cased Base model

The 1D Convolutional Neural Network achieved a test loss of 0.6471, a Macro-F1 score of 88.99%, and an accuracy of 90.32%. The weighted F1 scores further highlighted its effective classification capability across categories, with Method at 90.59%, Background at 91.53%, and Result at 84.87%.

Figure 18. SciBERT Based Models: Performance Comparison between Cased and Uncased Versions. These plots show a comparison based on Accuracy scores (above) and Macro-F1 scores (below) between the models obtained utilizing the two versions (Uncased and Cased) of SciBERT as baselines.

4.2. Galactica (Mini) based models

In this section, are detailed the outcomes associated with the Galactica (Small) based models (see **Figure 19**).

4.2.1. Fine-Tuning with Population Based Training (PBT) - Galactica

The Galactica (Small) model, subjected to fine-tuning through Population Based Training, achieved an optimized configuration characterized by a batch size of **32**, a learning rate of approximately **1.78e-05**, and a weight decay of **0.01423**. The tokens were processed up to a maximum length of **256**. This configuration resulted in a test loss of 0.3180 and an overall test F1 score³⁸ of 86.27%, with category-specific F1 scores of 87.62% for Method, 89.51% for Background, and 81.69% for Result. The model's test accuracy was recorded at 87.74%.

This model can be found as *FTCIC_GalacticaSmall* (Paolini, 2024).

4.2.2. Ensemble Models Performance - Galactica

In this section are reported the results of Galactica (Small) based models, fine-tuned on the binary classification task. The three base models, together with the best meta-classifier can be found as *EnsCIC_GalacticaSmall* (Paolini, 2024).

4.2.2.1. Max Score Voting - Galactica

Utilizing the highest score voting strategy among the ensemble models, an accuracy of 87.95% and a Macro-F1-score of 86.06% were achieved. The F1 scores for the Method, Background, and Result categories reached 88%, 90%, and 80%, respectively.

³⁸ Whenever the metric is referenced as F1 in case of overall evaluations, please consider that it is intended Macro-F1.

4.2.2.2. Random Forest - Galactica

The Random Forest meta-classifier, tailored with a configuration of `'bootstrap': False`, `'class_weight': None`, `'criterion': 'gini'`, `'max_depth': 5`, `'min_samples_leaf': 3`, `'min_samples_split': 2`, `'n_estimators': 50`, reported an accuracy of 87.04%, and a Macro-F1 score of 85.12%. Instead, the F1 scores for Method, Background, and Result were 88%, 89%, and 78%, respectively.

4.2.2.3. XGBoost - Galactica

The XGBoost model, configured with `'gamma': 0`, `'learning_rate': 0.01`, `'max_depth': 3`, `'n_estimators': 100`, achieved an accuracy of 87.04% and a Macro-F1-score of 85.30%. The F1 scores across the categories were 88% for Method, 89% for Background, and 79% for Result.

4.2.2.4. K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN) - Galactica

Optimized with `41 neighbors`, the K-NN model demonstrated an accuracy of 87.36% and a Macro-F1-score of 85.60%. The category-specific F1 scores were 88% for Method, 89% for Background, and 79% for Result.

4.2.2.5. Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Galactica

The Support Vector Machine, configured with `'C': 0.01`, `'class_weight': 'balanced'`, `'gamma': 'auto'`, `'kernel': 'rbf'`, exhibited an accuracy of 87.25% and a Macro-F1-score of 85.50%. The F1 scores for Method, Background, and Result were 89%, 89%, and 79%, respectively.

4.2.2.6. Feed Forward Neural Network - Galactica

The Feed Forward Neural Network reported a test loss of 0.6720, a Macro-F1 score of 86.23%, and an accuracy of 87.84%. The model showed F1 scores of 88.03% for Method, 89.55% for Background, and 81.10% for Result, indicating its effectiveness in classifying citations across all categories.

4.2.2.7. 1D Convolutional Neural Network - Galactica

The evaluation of the 1D Convolutional Neural Network yielded a test loss of 0.6697, a Macro-F1 score of 86.13%, and an accuracy of 87.90%. The category-specific F1 scores were 87.99% for Method, 89.60% for Background, and 80.78% for Result, affirming the model's proficient classification capabilities.

Figure 19. *Galactica (Mini) Based Models: Performance Comparison.*

The plots above show a comparison between the performances of all the experiments conducted utilizing *Galactica-Mini* - sometimes called *Small* within this study - as base model. The first presents accuracy related results, while the second details the Macro-F1 scores obtained by these models.

4.3. XLNet (Cased) based models

This section delves into the performance (see **Figure 20**) and configuration specifics of the XLNet Base (Cased) models.

4.3.1. Fine-Tuning with Population Based Training (PBT) - XLNet

The XLNet Base (Cased) model, fine-tuned employing Population Based Training, culminated in a final configuration that comprised a batch size of **16**, a learning rate of approximately **1.39e-05**, and a weight decay of **0.01938**. The model processed tokens with a maximum length of **256**. This fine-tuning phase resulted in a test loss of 0.3318, an overall test F1 score of 86.02%, and a test accuracy of 87.31%. The category-specific F1 scores were reported as 88.43% for Method, 88.20% for Background, and 81.43% for Result. The model can be found as *FTCIC_XLNet* (Paolini, 2024).

4.3.2. Ensemble Models Performance - XLNet

In this section are reported the results of XLNet (Base Cased) based models, fine-tuned on the binary classification task. The three base models, together with the best meta-classifier can be found as *EnsCIC_XLNet* (Paolini, 2024).

4.3.2.1. Max Score Voting - XLNet

The max score voting technique, applied among the ensemble models, achieved a notably high accuracy of 89.19%, and a Macro-F1 score of 87.74%. The categories method, background, and result, respectively recorded Macro-F1 scores of 91%, 90%, and 82%.

4.3.2.2. Random Forest - XLNet

Configured with `'bootstrap': True`, `'class_weight': None`, `'criterion': 'entropy'`, `'max_depth': 3`, `'min_samples_leaf': 3`, `'min_samples_split': 2`, `'n_estimators': 10`, the Random Forest model exhibited an accuracy of 89.30% and a Macro-F1-score of 87.95%. The F1 scores for Method, Background, and Result were 91%, 90%, and 83%, respectively.

4.3.2.3. XGBoost - XLNet

The XGBoost ensemble, with a configuration of `'gamma': 0`, `'learning_rate': 0.01`, `'max_depth': 3`, `'n_estimators': 100`, reported an accuracy of 89.13%, a Macro-F1-score of 87.77%, and category-specific F1 scores of 90% for Method, 91% for Background, and 83% for Result.

4.3.2.4. K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN) - XLNet

The K-NN model, optimized with `77 neighbors`, reported an accuracy of 89.56% and a Macro-F1-score of 88.27%, with F1 scores of 90% for Method, 91% for Background, and 84% for Result.

4.3.2.5. Support Vector Machine (SVM) - XLNet

The SVM, configured with `'C': 0.1`, `'class_weight': None`, `'gamma': 'auto'`, `'kernel': 'rbf'`, achieved an accuracy of 89.35% and a Macro-F1-score of 87.98%, with F1 scores of 90% for Method, 91% for Background, and 83% for Result.

4.3.2.6. Feed Forward Neural Network - XLNet

The Feed Forward Neural Network recorded a test loss of 0.6584, a Macro-F1 score of 87.96%, and an accuracy of 89.35%. The category-specific F1 scores were 90.78% for Method, 90.49% for Background, and 82.62% for Result.

4.3.2.7. 1D Convolutional Neural Network - XLNet

The 1D Convolutional Neural Network yielded a test loss of 0.6499, a Macro-F1 score of 88.53%, and an accuracy of 89.83%. The weighted F1 scores across categories were 90.09% for Method, 91.19% for Background, and 84.31% for Result, showcasing its exceptional performance in classification tasks.

Figure 20. *XLNet Based Models: Performance Comparison.*

The plots above show a comparison between the performances of all the experiments conducted utilizing *XLNet Base (Cased)* as base model. The first presents accuracy related results, while the second details the Macro-F1 scores obtained by these models.

Results Summary & SOTA Comparison

Model	Strategy	Accuracy	Macro F1	Method F1	Background F1	Result F1
<i>SciBERT (Uncased)</i>	Fine Tuning with PBT	88.54%	87.06%	89.76%	89.61%	81.80%
	Ensemble + Majority voting	88.54%	87.35%	89%	90%	84%
	Ensemble + Random Forest	88.17%	86.85%	89%	89%	82%
	Ensemble + XGBoost	89.08%	87.77%	89%	90%	83%
	Ensemble + KNN	88.60%	87.33%	89%	90%	83%
	Ensemble + SVM	88.33%	87.12%	89%	89%	83%
	Ensemble + FFNN	88.97%	87.85%	89.38%	90.06%	84.09%
	Ensemble + IDCNN	88.81%	87.66%	88.83%	90.06%	84.07%
<i>SciBERT (Cased)</i>	Fine Tuning with PBT	88.27%	87.00%	88.68%	89.54%	82.78%
	Ensemble + Majority voting	88.33%	86.65%	91%	89%	80%
	Ensemble + Random Forest	88.70%	87.09%	90%	90%	81%
	Ensemble + XGBoost	88.54%	86.91%	91%	90%	80%
	Ensemble + KNN	88.86%	87.31%	91%	90%	81%
	Ensemble + SVM	88.43%	86.81%	90%	90%	81%
	Ensemble + FFNN	89.73%	88.41%	90.18%	90.99%	84.07%
	Ensemble + IDCNN	90.32%	88.99%	90.59%	91.53%	84.87%
<i>Galactica (Small)</i>	Fine Tuning with PBT	87.74%	86.27%	87.62%	89.51%	81.69%
	Ensemble + Majority voting	87.95%	86.06%	88%	90%	80%
	Ensemble + Random Forest	87.04%	85.12%	88%	89%	78%
	Ensemble + XGBoost	87.04%	85.30%	88%	89%	79%
	Ensemble + KNN	87.36%	85.60%	88%	89%	79%
	Ensemble + SVM	87.25%	85.50%	89%	89%	79%
	Ensemble + FFNN	87.84%	86.23%	88.03%	89.55%	81.10%
	Ensemble + IDCNN	87.90%	86.13%	87.99%	89.60%	80.78%
<i>XLNet (Cased)</i>	Fine Tuning with PBT	87.31%	86.02%	88.43%	88.20%	81.43%
	Ensemble + Majority voting	89.19%	87.74%	91%	90%	82%
	Ensemble + Random Forest	89.30%	87.95%	91%	90%	83%
	Ensemble + XGBoost	89.13%	87.77%	90%	91%	83%
	Ensemble + KNN	89.56%	88.27%	90%	91%	84%
	Ensemble + SVM	89.35%	87.98%	90%	91%	83%
	Ensemble + FFNN	89.35%	87.96%	90.78%	90.49%	82.62%
	Ensemble + IDCNN	89.83%	88.53%	90.09%	91.19%	84.31%
<i>ImpactCite (Current SOTA)</i>	//	//	88.93%	//	//	//
<i>CitePrompt</i>	//	//	86.33%	//	//	//
<i>SciBERT</i>	//	//	86.32%	//	//	//

Table 5. Summary Table of Results.

This table presents a comprehensive analysis and comparison between the models produced as outcome of this work of thesis, and the top three models for the SciCite Citation Intent Classification Dataset, focusing on their performance metrics. The leading model in this domain, known as ImpactCite (Mercier et al., 2020), sets the current benchmark for State Of The Art (SOTA) performance. However, it's important to note that ImpactCite's documentation lacks detailed reporting on category-specific F1 scores as well as the model's overall accuracy on the classification task.

The comparison outlined in the table reveals a significant insight: the majority of the models developed during this research project have outperformed the second and third-ranked models on the leaderboard. This achievement underscores the effectiveness of the methodologies and innovations applied in this work. Remarkably, one model emerging from this project has achieved the milestone of exceeding the performance of the current SOTA model, ImpactCite. This notable success highlights the potential of the new approaches and techniques implemented in the development of these models, setting a new benchmark for future research in the field of Citation Intent Classification.

Chapter 5
Discussion and Enhancement
Perspectives

5. Discussion and Enhancement Perspectives

In this study has been performed an extensive set of experiments (for an overview, see **Table 5**) involving various Language Models and techniques within the framework of the Citation Intent Classification (CIC) task. All the empirical evaluations involved the use of the SciCite dataset as the only datasource, thus no additional data outside of it have been used. These experiments culminated in notable advancements within the CIC domain. In particular, these investigations have produced a model that exceeds the current state-of-the-art (SOTA), as well as many other models that surpass the second and third positions in the benchmark (see **Figure 21**).

The analyses were mainly focused on Language Models (LMs), Ensemble Strategies, Fine-Tuning, and Hyperparameter Optimization. Each of these macro-domains will be discussed within this section, offering useful insights into the dynamics of Citation Intent Classification, and revealing both the potential and the limitations of current methodologies.

Figure 21. Macro-F1 score Comparison between Benchmark Models and Best Models of This Study.

This plot offers a comparison between the Macro-F1 performances of the best models (one for each baseline LM) obtained in this study, against the three benchmark models. *EnsCIC_SciBERT_Cased* (green) surpasses the current SOTA (red), and also shows significant performance improvements against other *SciBERT* based models (blue).

5.1. Evaluating the Efficacy of Population Based Training in Enhancing Model Performance

The investigation into models' fine-tuning, augmented with Population Based Training (PBT) and fine-grained evaluations, highlights both the relevance and utility of this technique in boosting models' performances. This is particularly evident with SciBERT, for which extensive literature in the CIC domain was produced (Beltagy et al., 2019; Lahiri et al., 2023). For Galactica and XLNet the situation is slightly different, indeed Galactica was never employed for CIC related tasks, and for what concerns XLNet instead, one of its derived models, namely *ImpactCite* (Mercier et al., 2020), was the previous SOTA benchmark before this study, but it was not possible to replicate or further enhance the results obtained by this model.

Going back to SciBERT, it is possible to notice that by the integration of PBT with both the Uncased and Cased versions of the base model, this study has achieved significant enhancements w.r.t. previous benchmarks (**Table 5**). These results underline the impact and utility of the particular training procedure adopted. The application of PBT, together with the integration of a fine-grained model's evaluation, have emerged as critical factors in this fine-tuning process, indeed this procedure has evidently optimized model parameters more effectively, thereby increasing the ability of SciBERT in dealing with the task at hand. This adaptive method of fine-tuning mainly emphasizes the role and significance of hyperparameter search and optimization techniques in reaching peak performances, thus suggesting that the model's ceiling is influenced not only by its architecture but strongly depends also by the configuration of its hyperparameters.

5.1.1. Comparative Insights on Architectural and Lexical Advantages

A comparative analysis of SciBERT against models such as Galactica and XLNet, which are based on different architectures and training methodologies, further highlights the essential role of the underlying architecture in obtaining better classification outcomes. The encoder-only architecture, exemplified by SciBERT, has shown a clear advantage in the classification task - as expected -, in particular over decoder-only models like the ones based on Galactica, thereby reinforcing the idea of encoder-only models being a better fit for this kind of applications. This conclusion is also derived by the similarity in domain-specific pre-training of both Galactica and SciBERT, with both

their vocabularies containing scientific lexicon, and their understanding of academic and scientific language. Nevertheless, within the scope of this thesis, it was not possible to evaluate larger versions of Galactica models³⁹, leaving some open questions concerning their potential superiority over the models discussed. Furthermore, being Galactica models mainly devised for language generation tasks, it would be interesting to research and understand their performances in prompt-learning based frameworks.

Instead, the divergence in performances between SciBERT and XLNet models accentuates the importance of domain-specific pre-training. This is also particularly evident in the study by Beltagy et al. (2019), where the base BERT model's performances are compared with the performances obtained by SciBERT. SciBERT's pre-training on scientific literature bestows it with a unique advantage for tasks within the scientific domain, an insight further confirmed by this study, and that could guide future model development efforts, but also suggest even more specific domain adaptations to integrate within the fine-tuning process in a sequential way. Despite XLNet's more advanced training approach, SciBERT's domain-specific vocabulary grants it a competitive edge in tasks closely aligned with its training corpus. This lexical advantage is evident in the disparity of Macro-F1 scores between SciBERT and XLNet models, illustrating the significant impact of specialized vocabulary in domain-relevant classification tasks.

5.1.2. Some Possibilities to Further Enhance SciBERT PBT-Based Fine-Tuning

This progress suggests additional explorations into this and different methods, which may enhance the performances of SciBERT-based models even further. Indeed, a direct approach to increasing the benefits of PBT involves increasing the number - thus also the diversity - of agents within the PBT population. A larger population size grants a wider exploration of the hyperparameter space, potentially leading to configurations that yield better performances. This expansion should also enhance the overall utility of the evolutionary dynamics of PBT, providing for a more robust optimization process through the *natural* selection of the most effective models within a greater set.

³⁹ Galactica models are: *mini* (125 M parameters), *base* (1.3 B parameters), *standard* (6.7 B parameters), *large* (30 B parameters), and *huge* (120 B parameters) (Taylor et al., 2022)

Furthermore, another possibility involves the integration of elements from other evolutionary algorithms into the PBT training. Some techniques from Genetic Algorithms (GAs), such as *crossover*, could be integrated within the PBT framework to foster a more dynamic exploration of the parameter space. The potential for enhancing the performance of SciBERT-based models through advanced PBT techniques is particularly appealing. By expanding the population size and integrating sophisticated optimization strategies, the fine-tuning process could be significantly improved.

5.2. Advancing Beyond Benchmarks: The Synergistic Power of Ensemble Models

As highlighted by the preceding section, it is evident from this study that ensemble models typically outperform their fine-tuned counterparts across most scenarios, with the notable exception being the Galactica (Mini) model. The exemplary performance of these ensemble models underlines the synergistic potential inherent in combining multiple base models, which facilitates a more precise and comprehensive exploration of the data landscape, enabling the ensemble, together with its meta-classifier head, to identify intricate patterns and relationships within the data. The ensemble approach inherently embodies the principle that the whole is better than the sum of its parts, with each base model filling in the gaps left by the others, leading to a more accurate and robust classification capability (Mohammed and Kora, 2023).

Another interesting discussion around the ensemble-based experiments of this work is based on how the meta-classifier head is capable of identifying intricate patterns that go beyond the simple Max-Scoring vote system. To be clearer, it is extremely interesting to see that, even if the heads of the ensembles are solely trained upon the raw percentages produced by the base models, these are capable of identifying biases within the output predictions. A brief example should clarify this point: if the three baseline models output the following percentages 98%, 91%, and 23%, it is natural to think that the correct one is the first because it is more confident w.r.t. its classification. Let's suppose that, instead, the head chooses the second class (91%) and that its classification is correct. This implies that the head has identified and mapped some particular patterns that arise directly from percentages, identifying thus some weaknesses of base models in particular situations.

This hypothesis is also confirmed by the difference in performances that can be seen when comparing the best ensemble + head, against the max score voting system. This situation arises in the majority of cases, being - again - Galactica (Mini) the only exception. Such a hypothesis is worth to be investigated deeply with further studies, but these experimental results open the door for even higher ceilings in ensemble model performances within the CIC task.

Finally, the ensemble model *EnsCIC_SciBERT_Cased* (Paolini, 2024) variant has exceeded the current benchmark, establishing a new standard for State-Of-The-Art (SOTA) benchmarks. Alongside, a majority of the ensemble models have also outstripped the second-ranked model in the leaderboard. The following are the top performers beside *EnsCIC_SciBERT_Cased* (see **Figure 21**) from each base model category:

1. *EnsCIC_XLNet* (Paolini, 2024);
2. *FTCIC_GalacticaSmall* (Paolini, 2024);
3. *EnsCIC_SciBERT_Uncased* (Paolini, 2024).

5.2.1. Possible Pathways towards the improvement of Ensemble models

The potential for further enhancing the robustness and performance of these ensemble models is almost infinite. One avenue for improvement involves experimenting with a broader array of base models. Furthermore, the integration of additional base models grounded in diverse Language Models (LMs), or the use of retroactive training techniques could further refine the ensembles' effectiveness. Retroactive training, in particular, offers an intriguing approach by recalibrating the ensemble based on the identified weaknesses of base models, thereby optimizing the overall performance. This retroactive process may also be extremely beneficial: seen the ability of meta-classifier heads to identify patterns from only raw percentages, it is possible to imagine how much this capability may further be improved when the head training is smoothly integrated within the base models fine-tuning, thus when the head communicates with the baseline models and provides a more precise direction for weight adjustments. Finally, the integration of Population Based Training (PBT) in the training regimen of the base binary LMs presents another promising strategy for enhancement.

Enhancement possibilities are detailed below:

- **Expanding Base Model Diversity:** Exploring a wider selection of base models could highlight new synergies within the ensemble, leveraging the unique strengths of varied architectures.
- **Cross-Architecture Base Models:** Utilizing base models from multiple language model architectures could provide a richer feature set for the ensemble to draw upon.
- **Retroactive Training:** This technique adjusts the ensemble's strategy based on the performance of base models, targeting their specific weaknesses for a more balanced and effective overall performance.
- **PBT for Base Models:** Applying Population Based Training to base models may potentially optimize their performances, even before these LMs are integrated into the ensemble, potentially leading to a stronger collective output.

The strategies outlined above are not isolated, or mutually exclusive; rather, they offer a synergistic potential that can be applied in combination across a broad spectrum of applications. Integrating and testing these approaches collectively allows for the exploration of their additive effect on the enhancement of models performances.

5.2.1.1. Knowledge Distillation

In addition to the strategies previously mentioned for enhancing the performance of ensemble models, incorporating *Knowledge Distillation* (KD) (Hinton et al., 2015) presents another possible pathway. Knowledge Distillation involves transferring knowledge from a complex, often larger model (*teacher*) to a simpler, smaller model (*student*), aiming to retain the performance benefits of the teacher model while gaining the efficiency advantages of the student model (You et al., 2021). This technique may be particularly advantageous in ensemble settings, where the distilled knowledge from multiple or highly complex models can be consolidated into more compact models that are easier to train and deploy, without significant loss in accuracy.

Possible advantages derived from the use of KD are related to:

1. **Efficiency and Performance:** KD can significantly enhance the efficiency of ensemble models by distilling the collective knowledge into a single and more manageable model. This not only simplifies the deployment process but can also maintain, or in some cases, improve the performance of the distilled model compared to its teacher. Additionally, the use of this single model may also speed up computations for retroactive training.
2. **Model Simplification:** By applying KD, the complexity of managing multiple base models within the ensemble can be reduced. This simplification aids in the practical application of these models, especially in resource-constrained environments. This may also be beneficial in the case of an extended base of binary LMs.
3. **Enhanced Generalization:** KD has the potential to improve the generalization capabilities of the student model by learning from the *soft outputs* (i.e., probabilities) of the teacher models, which contain rich information about the relationships between different classes.
4. **Customization and Flexibility:** The process of knowledge distillation can be customized based on the specific needs and constraints of the ensemble models, allowing for flexible integration of diverse architectures and training strategies.

Also, the integration of knowledge distillation into the enhancement strategies for ensemble models could synergize with the previously proposed methods, such as expanding base model diversity, utilizing cross-architecture base models, employing retroactive training, and applying Population Based Training to base models. The combined use of these techniques along with Knowledge Distillation opens up a vast amount of possibilities for optimizing ensemble models in natural language processing tasks, and more specifically for the aim of this project.

5.3. Additional Considerations on Domain Adaptation and Evolutionary Algorithms

This section aims to highlight some theoretical implications derived from the results of this work, in particular, emphasizing the role of Domain Adaptation steps, and of Evolutionary Algorithms for hyperparameter optimization.

5.3.1. Domain-Specific Model Adaptation

The results of this study shed light on the importance of domain-specific adaptations in NLP models. The distinct overall performance advantages observed with SciBERT, which were probably derived by its domain-specific pre-training - also confirmed by previous studies (Beltagy et al., 2019; Cohan et al., 2019) in different scenarios -, and the good performances obtained by the Galactica (Mini) model despite its decoder-only setup, confirm that for NLP tasks closely tied to specialized fields, the incorporation of domain-specific knowledge and vocabulary is not just beneficial but essential. This additional confirmation pushes for a deeper evaluation of how pre-training corpora are selected and suggests that future model development could benefit from an even more granular approach to domain specificity.

5.3.2. Evolutionary Algorithms in Model Optimization

The application of Population Based Training (PBT) in this research highlights the great potential of evolutionary algorithms when integrated into the fine-tuning of language models. Traditionally, the hesitation to use these algorithms has been linked to their significant demand for computational resources and prohibitive training times (Bai, 2021). However, this study demonstrates that, with careful planning involving mixed precision training, detailed evaluations, and early stopping mechanisms, it is possible to efficiently train language models using such advanced optimization strategies without the need for high computational resources⁴⁰. The partition of CPU and GPU resources is also crucial in this efficient approach, mainly for parallelization purposes. Further exploration of techniques such as QLoRA (Dettmers et al., 2023) or LoftQ (Li et al., 2023) might offer additional improvements.

⁴⁰ Additional investigations are needed to detail the amount of computational resources needed and to quantify precisely how much the use of these strategies reduces the impact on computational demands.

In specific experiments documented in the *CIC Framework* (Paolini, 2024), also the strategy of freezing some initial layers within the models was employed to speed up the training process, decrease memory demands, and preserve the original models' ability to generalize. This method, along with pruning strategies, appears to be another way to optimize the fine-tuning process efficiently. Moreover, adopting adaptive training methods (Chen et al., 2020) and optimizers (Zhuang et al., 2020) for large language models (LLMs) could substantially reduce the use of resources while maintaining model accuracy.

5.4. An Investigation on Feature Importance

The outcomes of this research have implications that reach also into practical realms, going beyond theoretical enhancements in the CIC task and in the fine-tuning of language models. The exemplary performance achieved by the SciBERT Cased model, boosted by advanced methodologies such as Population Based Training (PBT) and strategic ensemble modeling, lays a solid background for the creation of reliable tools aimed at facilitating academic research. Such tools, equipped with the capability to perform bibliometric analysis and automatize the classification of scholarly texts and citations, promise to push a bit further the efficiency and depth of academic research.

Acknowledged that, and given the superior performance showcased by the ensemble based on the SciBERT Cased models, this study went further into exploring the model's versatility and generalization capabilities across different conditions. This exploration was mainly focused on assessing the model's performance in a scenario characterized by the reduction of available features. Thereby, an ensemble configuration of SciBERT Cased was developed and evaluated in contexts where section titles were omitted, to analyze the model's capacity to decipher the inherent semantic content of citations and accurately classify them into the correct categories, without the need to rely on this specific contextual information. This additional experimental phase was designed to investigate the adaptability of the SciBERT Cased model and its capacity to maintain robust generalization even when deprived of certain features that might be presumed crucial for classification accuracy. The objective was to verify whether the model could effectively leverage its understanding of citation semantics in the absence of explicit structural indicators like section titles,

thereby providing insights into the model's ability to extract and utilize the core meaning of texts for classification purposes.

5.4.1. Feature Importance and Model Versatility

The evaluation of the SciBERT Cased model's capabilities in the context where section titles were not provided yielded the following results:

- **Macro-F1 Score:** 87.75%
- **Per-class F1 Score:**
 - **Method:** 87.85%
 - **Background:** 90.50%
 - **Result:** 84.91%
- **Test Accuracy:** 88.86%

These results, while impressive, are lower than those achieved by the ensemble model with section titles included as features (see **Figure 22**). This discrepancy highlights the critical role that specific features, such as section titles⁴¹, play in enhancing model performance. It also serves as a practical demonstration of the concept of feature importance in machine learning, showing how the inclusion or exclusion of certain features can significantly impact the outcomes of classification tasks.

Figure 22. *Section vs Non-Section based Training Results.*
Comparison chart between the ensemble model incorporating section titles and the ensemble model excluding section titles

⁴¹ But also prompt engineering.

5.4.1.1. The Possible Role of Feature Ablation Studies

Moving forward, the integration of feature ablation studies with prompt engineering techniques in more controlled settings represents a logical progression for future research within the CIC domain. Indeed, according to O'Connor and Andreas (2021), Transformer-based language models benefit from conditioning on contexts of hundreds to thousands of previous tokens, thus suggesting for an enhanced understanding of which of these lexical and syntactical features contribute to a more accurate classification and/or prediction. In environments that have at their core LMs, the application of advanced prompt engineering strategies offers a methodical approach to further analyze the influence of specific features on model performance. By modifying prompts and assessing the impact on model responses with the inclusion or exclusion of certain features, it may thereby be possible to achieve a clearer understanding of how each feature contributes to the model's effectiveness. This methodical approach not only would deepen the understanding of the significance of individual features but may also provide useful insights into the strategic use of prompt engineering to refine models for particular tasks. Combining controlled feature ablation studies with the thoughtful application of prompt engineering could lead to improvements in both model precision and task alignment.

The performance of the SciBERT Cased model, both with and without section titles, not only exemplifies the model's versatility but also highlights the importance of a careful selection of textual features within the chosen prompt to achieve better results. As demonstrated, even without the inclusion of section titles, the Ensemble of SciBERT Cased models maintain really good performance levels, still outperforming the second and third models of the benchmark. Nevertheless, such performances are surpassed by the ensemble model when such contextual features are included, thereby suggesting for a deeper investigation also within additional features that may be relevant, and the overall structure of the textual inputs for the CIC task.

5.5. Challenges and Constraints

This chapter delves into the various challenges and constraints encountered during this study. While the research yielded some notable insights in the field of natural language processing, particularly in Citation Intent Classification, it was not without its set of difficulties. Such problems are related to limitations in computational resources and complexities in the implementation and integration of advanced training methodologies, such as Population Based Training with fine-grained evaluation.

5.5.1. Limited Resources for Larger Models

One of the main limitations encountered within this research was the constrained access to the computational resources necessary for conducting experiments with the larger configurations of the Galactica models. Galactica, with its proven efficacy in processing scientific texts, needs significant computational resources for both training and fine-tuning to express its full potential⁴². This requirement became a limiting factor, narrowing the research scope as it prevented a comprehensive exploration of these more extensive models, which could have potentially revealed more profound insights and achieved superior performance metrics. A solution that has been tested within the framework involved the use of batch accumulation steps, but even with this strategic implementation, the Google Colab A100 GPU was not sufficient to efficiently train and evaluate such models.

All the experiments carried out within this study were conducted using the Google Colab A100 GPU, a decision that aimed to maximize the available resources efficiently. The NVIDIA A100 GPU is equipped with relatively high computational capabilities - in particular when compared to the actual economical costs of other possibilities -, including 40GB of GPU memory and a bandwidth that significantly accelerates data transfer speeds. The A100's architecture, designed also to deliver enhanced performance for deep learning applications, has offered a robust platform for the experiments of this framework, allowing for the exploration of advanced model training and fine-tuning techniques within the confines of available resources.

⁴² In particular when it comes to larger versions of the model.

5.5.2. Adapting PBT for LMs Fine-Tuning

Adapting Population Based Training to the fine-tuning process, especially when integrating fine-grained evaluation techniques, presented a significant challenge. PBT's dynamic approach to searching within the hyperparameter space becomes particularly complex when integrated with detailed and frequent evaluations. This complexity derives also from the need to continuously monitor and adjust the training process based on empirical evaluations concerning the efficiency and efficacy of the ongoing process. Moreover, another challenging aspect is related to maintaining and resuming the training process after each exploration and evaluation step. Identifying the correct elements to store in the checkpoint dictionary and implementing effective strategies for reloading the training process exactly from the epoch and batch where it was paused added many layers of complexity to the ideation of the training loop. Indeed, the precise resumption needed a detailed understanding of the training state - including the model parameters -, the optimizer state, and the exact position within the dataset. Finally, storing checkpoint information and developing precise mechanisms to reload data to smoothly continue the training loop required a meticulous planning. These efforts were critical in preserving the integrity of the training process and ensuring that the advanced PBT methodology could be applied without sacrificing the efficiency or effectiveness of model fine-tuning.

5.5.3. A brief insight into Reproducibility

The reproducibility crisis in science has emerged as a great concern across various disciplines, casting doubts over the reliability of numerous research works. In his study, Baker (2016) shows how, within the scientific community, a significant number of researchers deal with reproducibility-related problems, some are not able to reproduce other's experiments, and some are not capable of reproducing their works. This acknowledgment, from over 1500 surveyed scientists, reveals the pervasive nature of the reproducibility crisis, suggesting that it is not confined to some particular fields, but is a widespread issue affecting the totality of scientific domains.

To better understand the nature of such a crisis, Meng (2020) suggests an innovative perspective on it. The author provides a better definition of what reproducibility in the research landscape means, differentiating it from replicability, and shifting the focus on how these two central components of trustworthy research build the concept of reliability. By providing such differentiation, Meng

underlines the need for clear definitions and, in particular, for rigorous methodologies to efficiently face the reproducibility crisis, emphasizing the role of data science as a pivotal element. Finally, Peng (2015) tries to identify the nature of this widespread crisis in the lack of analytical skills from within the scientific community. The author argues, and strongly pushes for a more robust application of statistical principles and data science methodologies in scientific research, in order to enhance reproducibility, providing a bulwark against this crisis. A disciplined approach, together with rigorous data analysis and strategic experimental design may help to solve this pervasive problem. Reproducibility problems have been faced also within this research work, not all the data sources nor models were openly accessible or easy to test - mainly because of the lack of an adequate description of the steps to perform - leading to some difficulties in testing assumptions and in reproducing the results of previous works.

Together, these works draw a comprehensive picture of the reproducibility crisis, highlighting its implications for the credibility of scientific research and the trust placed in scientific findings by the public and the scientific community alike. They call for a synergistic effort to address the underlying causes of the crisis, advocating for enhanced transparency, methodological rigor, and the adoption of statistical and data science tools as indispensable elements of the solution. The open accessibility to codes and workflows has a central role in healing the crisis. This is one of the main reasons why whatever has been produced within this research is openly available, cited, referenced, and easily accessible. This extends to models, source codes, and to the implementations of the workflows designed for this project.

5.5.4. Dataset Imbalance and Data Scarcity

Another challenge that this research project had to deal with is related to the scarcity of data within the SciCite dataset, and its inherent class imbalance. As shown in **Figure 3**, the SciCite dataset's label distribution is highly skewed. The overrepresentation of the Background class, in particular when compared against the number of datapoints of the Result class, represents a problem, and this is particularly visible within all the models trained over this dataset, which fail to classify Result instances with the precision that these show over the other two classes. As can be further inspected within **Table 5**, all the models produced within this framework have a specific Result class F1 that is highly lower with respect to the F1 scores of the other two classes, such difference ranges from 10 to 6 percentage points in the majority of the cases when compared against the Background

specific scores. This difference can easily be attributed to the evident class imbalance of this dataset. Moreover, not only the represented classes are imbalanced, but the Result class contains at most 1000 datapoints for training⁴³, which are not sufficient to provide a comprehensive representation of this category.

Within this study, the main strategy adopted to face this issue, beside the employment of ensemble strategies (Liu et al., 2022), revolved around Weighted Loss functions, but this was not sufficient to solve the problem, which is deeply rooted in the scarcity of Result instances. Thus, some possibilities to face this scarcity are presented here. The first, and more direct possibility involves the integration of the SciCite dataset with other datasets produced for the CIC task. Nevertheless, this is not an easy option, in particular, because of the different classification schemes employed by the other datasets, but also because the extracted context does not always maintain a coherent structure across different datasources. Within the CIC domain, it is thus extremely important to find a general schema, that may be applicable to different sources, and that is as general as possible and as specific as necessary with respect to the needs of these citation-based applications. In this way it would be possible to guarantee interoperability between datasets, making their integration immediate.

5.5.4.1. Data Augmentation Techniques

Besides the various possibilities with data integration, another possible solution to overcome the data scarcity issue is represented by Data Augmentation (DA) techniques. Within the domain of DA, there is a wide array of possibilities to solve such problem. In particular, during the last years, many new techniques that leverage the impressive capabilities of LMs came out, such as the disrupting back-and-forth transaction for DA (Sennrich et al., 2016). Ranging from devising new documents and terms weighting schemes, such as the DFS weighting schema proposed by Chen et al. (2021), to modifications of the original sentences. Some DA techniques may be particularly relevant and useful in the context of the CIC task. Besides all the methods revolving around LM capabilities, which induce data augmentation by the generation of new sentences (Yang and Li, 2023; Feng et al., 2021; Bayer et al., 2022).

⁴³ While, Background has a bit less than 5000 instances, and Result has around 2000 instances.

In particular, it would be interesting to apply the following techniques:

- **AEDA (An Easier Data Augmentation)**: a newly devised and easier implementation of the original **EDA** (Wei and Zou, 2019), which at the same time provides for better performances. AEDA involves the random insertion of punctuation marks within the texts, and it changes the positions of the words while keeping intact their order of appearance within the sentence, providing thus more generalized performances (Karimi et al., 2021) (see **Figure 23**).

Data augmentation	Description	Examples
No	Original sentence	I did not like movies, but the popcorn was good.
EDA (Wei & Zou, 2019)	Synonym replacement (Randomly select words in the sentence and replace them with their synonyms.)	I did not like movies, besides the popcorn was good.
	Random insertion (Randomly select synonyms for words in the sentence and insert them into the sentence)	I did not like movies, but the popcorn was no good.
	Random swap (Randomly choose two words in the sentence and swap their positions.)	I did like movies, but the popcorn was not good.
	Random deletion (Randomly select some words from the sentence and delete them.)	I did like movies, but the popcorn was good.
AEDA (Karimi et al., 2021)	Random insertion of punctuation marks into the original sentence.	I did not, like movies, but the popcorn was good?

Figure 23. EDA vs AEDA: Exemplar Comparison of Working Dynamics. Comparison of EDA (Wei and Zou, 2019) and AEDA (Karimi et al., 2021). Image taken from Long et al. (2023).

- **AWD (Adversarial Word Dilution)**: this method is extremely efficient in training low-resource text classification models, and it operates by generating hard positive examples by diluting the embeddings of strong positive words by a weighted mix with unknown word embeddings (Chen et al., 2023) (see **Figure 24**).

Figure 24. AWD technique mechanics. With ϕ representing the main text classifier, and θ_{y_i} representing dilution network blocks. Image taken from Chen et al. (2023).

- **VWI (Virtual Word Insertion)**: this method has been devised to generate new sentences by randomly inserting *virtual* words into existing sentences. Such virtual words are basically *embedded words* generated by computing the average word embedding of all words in the sentence, and this can be done with two different methods: unweighted average and weighted average (Long et al., 2023).

By leveraging the power of DA techniques, it could be possible to overcome data scarcity limitations, thus surpassing the base ceiling set up in this research.

Chapter 6

CIC Application

6. CIC Application

This chapter delves into the practical employment of the previously reported state-of-the-art (SOTA) ensemble model obtained within this study, realized through the development of a web application powered by Flask⁴⁴. The use of Flask, a lightweight and versatile web framework, facilitates the smooth integration of this model, together with the other variant trained with no sections, into a user-friendly, web-based platform. This chapter aims to provide a comprehensive overview of this tool.

6.1. General Aim and Introduction

This application was created within the GraspOS⁴⁵ project, dedicated at building a data infrastructure, and at promoting an ethical research assessment system based on the principles of the Open Science (OS)⁴⁶ movement within Europe. Indeed, GraspOS aims at supporting the *European Open Science Cloud* (EOSC) ecosystem thanks to the integration of tools and frameworks that track the use of research services while pushing towards the adoption of OS principles. Citation data turns out to be a key element of this process, promoting openness, legitimacy, and knowledge sharing within academic communities, recalling some of the main principles behind both GraspOS and Open Science.

The developed classifier represents the second component of a more complete and comprehensive application, which has as its final aim the automated extraction of citation intents from PDF files and their subsequent classification (*opencitations/cec: alpha version (service)*). Pagnotta and Paolini, 2024). The tool described within this thesis covers indeed the classification part, and it is composed by a backend software aimed at loading different models in different situations and at classifying the citation contexts passed as input, and by a frontend user interface developed with Flask and yet publicly available⁴⁷.

⁴⁴ <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/3.0.x/>

⁴⁵ <https://graspos.eu/>

⁴⁶ The European Commission defines Open Science as a digital and collaborative approach to a quick dissemination of knowledge.

⁴⁷ <http://test.opencitations.net:81/cic/classifier>

6.2. Design and Implementation

This section will present details about the backend architecture, and the frontend interface. But, before diving deeper in configuration detail, it is worth saying that even if the base models are trained to classify contexts into three possible classes, the final tool provides for four possible classification outcomes. This is due to the addition of a human defined threshold on the three base models predictions: if none of these three base models outputs a confidence higher than 90%, the classification process is considered unreliable. This particular addition has been proposed in the Alpha version of this software but it is clear - in particular in light of the conclusions derived in the previous chapter - that the metaclassifier head plays an essential role in discerning and correcting base models biases, thus suggesting a more suitable framework for unreliable classifications.

Finally, it is also worth to notice that the three base labels, together with the unreliable class, have been mapped in order to represent four object properties within the Citation Typing Ontology (CiTO)(Shotton 2010). In particular, Background became *obtainsBackgroundFrom*⁴⁸, Method is *usesMethodIn*⁴⁹, Result is *usesConclusionsFrom*⁵⁰, and finally Unreliable maps to a general purpose object property: *citesForInformation*⁵¹. This mapping has been driven by two main reasons. First, in order to enhance the understandability of the resulting classification, and second, in light of possible future works. Indeed, by employing Semantic Web technologies and standards, such as the Resource Description Framework (RDF) and Web Ontology Language (OWL), this mapping facilitates the integration of the citation classification tool into broader digital library ecosystems and scholarly communication networks. The use of CiTO properties specifically allows for a semantically rich description of the relationships between citations that goes beyond the mere acknowledgment, or reference. This semantic enrichment additionally enables several advanced functionalities. For instance, it allows for automated reasoning over citation networks, an aspect that will be detailed in Chapter 7, or could also contribute to the ongoing efforts to improve the transparency and reproducibility of research by explicitly modeling the relationships between research methods, results, and background information.

⁴⁸ <http://purl.org/spar/cito/obtainsBackgroundFrom>

⁴⁹ <http://purl.org/spar/cito/usesMethodIn>

⁵⁰ <http://purl.org/spar/cito/usesConclusionsFrom>

⁵¹ <http://purl.org/spar/cito/citesForInformation>

6.2.1. Architectural Overview

The entire software revolves around the **Predictor** object, which is the class that actually carries out the final predictions. This object, beside its prediction functionalities, is also the one that deal with the retrieve and setting of GPU devices if available, and to do this it takes into account also the possible different architecture within machine processors, strategically finding the correct mapping for the device at hand.

Additionally, the **Predictor** class takes is responsible of the general tokenization process organization, which depends mainly on the kind of model the final user wants to utilize. In particular, different tokenization processes are devised for sections-based data, and for non-sections-based data, together with the possibility to deal with mixed case scenarios. This method smoothly call the **tokenizer** within the correct classifier class. Furthermore, **Predictor** deals with the creation of a final JSON file, which can be downloaded within the interface by the final user and, finally, it carries out also the initialization of both the base binary models, and of the metaclassifier head, again accordingly to sections, no-sections, and mixed cases.

Beside this main object, the backend of the CIC application is composed by four additional classes. **EnsembleClassifier**, which carries out the loading of base models from the server, in accordance with the instruction provided by the **Predictor** object. **DataProcessor** which is responsible for all the data preprocessing steps, such as reading and formatting data in text and JSON forms, generating IDs, mapping data instances, and doing all the structural checks needed for a correct formatting of input data. Finally, the **SectionsMetaClassifierCNN** and **NoSectionsMetaClassifierCNN** are the objects containing the architectures of the metaclassifier heads.

6.2.2. User Interface

The interface has been produced by means of the Flask library, integrated with HTML to define the overall structure, CSS for styling and esthetically pleasant choices, and JavaScript for providing interactivity to this application. The resulting design is extremely minimal, it provides an overview of the tool, some relevant aspects of the backend architecture, and simple instructions for simple usage. The final user, through this minimalistic interface, has the possibility to easily add data both

in the form of a list of tuples (textual data), or to directly upload a JSON file which respects the structural definition provided in the classifier page.

Additionally, users have also the possibility to choose which mode better fits their data. Indeed, through the toggle of a simple button (*Mixed*, *With Section Titles*, or *Without Section Titles*), it is possible to choose whether the tool will analyze data by considering or not sections - if present - within the data, or to classify contexts in a mixed mode (default mode), which will use section-based models for datapoints containing section information, and no-section-based models for datapoints without this additional element (see **Figure 25**).

Figure 25. *UI of the web-based Application.*
Detail of the User Interface of the classification component.

Finally, end users just have to click the *Classify* button to start the backend process and classify the contexts provided as textual input, or click the *Classify JSON* button whether data were uploaded through a JSON file. The results of this classification are reported immediately after the end of this process, together with additional details to elucidate the decision making process carried out by the Ensemble strategy (see **Figure 26**). An additional possibility provided to end users is to download an informative JSON file, containing data and metadata about citations and classification results.

Sentence: 0

SECTION: 4. Discussion

CITATION: This was expected, as the literature has shown that ethylene has an inhibitory effect on some forms of growth, such as internode elongation (e.g. Love et al., 2009) and hypocotyl elongation (e.g. Pierik et al., 2006).

BACKGROUND BINARY POSITIVE PROBABILITY: 0.953326940536499

METHOD BINARY POSITIVE PROBABILITY: 0.019519705325365067

RESULT BINARY POSITIVE PROBABILITY: 0.22100810706615448

BACKGROUND MODEL CONFIDENCE: 0.99770587682724

METHOD MODEL CONFIDENCE: 0.0006429615314118564

RESULT MODEL CONFIDENCE: 0.0016511579742655158

FINAL PREDICTION: obtainsBackgroundFrom (BACKGROUND)

Sentence: 1

SECTION: DISCUSSIONS

CITATION: These data are consistent with previous reports that exposure of the developing brain to NMDA antagonists such as ketamine or PCP results in widespread and dose-dependent apoptotic neurodegeneration (Ikonomidou et al., 1999, 2001; JevtovicTodorovic et al., 2003; Olney et al., 2002).

BACKGROUND BINARY POSITIVE PROBABILITY: 0.011469509452581406

METHOD BINARY POSITIVE PROBABILITY: 0.01722501777112484

RESULT BINARY POSITIVE PROBABILITY: 0.9721613526344299

BACKGROUND MODEL CONFIDENCE: 0.0003410683711990714

METHOD MODEL CONFIDENCE: 0.0032902141101658344

RESULT MODEL CONFIDENCE: 0.9963687658309937

FINAL PREDICTION: usesConclusionsFrom (RESULT)

Figure 26. *UI of the Results Presented by the Web-based Application.*

Snapshot of the results provided by the model for some citation contexts (visible in **CITATION**) together with the sections in which are found (**SECTION**). The **BINARY POSITIVE PROBABILITIES** refer to the outputs provided by the base binary models, while the **MODEL CONFIDENCES** refer to the final probabilities dictated by the metaclassifier head. The **FINAL PREDICTION** instead represents the class assigned to the citation by the ensemble model.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Future Works

7. Conclusions and Future Works

The primary objective of this thesis was to explore the role of advanced hyperparameter optimization methodologies and ensemble strategies when applied to Language Models (LMs) fine-tuning, in order to see whether leveraging these techniques may lead to overall performances and efficacies comparable - or even superior - to the current benchmarks for the Citation Intent Classification (CIC) task. The discussion starts in Chapter 2, which provides a comprehensive overview of the CIC task, addressing the challenges in selecting an appropriate citation classification schema and in creating robust, multidisciplinary, interoperable, and comprehensive datasets. Additionally, this chapter delves into existent methodologies to deal with the CIC task, starting from the first experiments of semi-automated methods, and proceeding up to the current use of Language Models, of which a general taxonomy is provided.

Chapter 3, starting with the presentation of the three LMs used within the context of this research, explores the methodological development of the framework devised for answering the original research question. This chapter investigates the specifics of each LM - SciBERT, Galactica, and XLNet -, detailing their unique contributions and potential in addressing the classification task. It further elaborates on the experimental design, and outlines the creation of a sophisticated fine-tuning approach that incorporates a Population Based Training (PBT) scheduler for hyperparameters search and optimization, as well as the practical development of an Ensemble strategy.

Chapter 4 details the outcomes of this research work, offering a factual analysis of the performances achieved by the different strategies based on the three Language Models. It does it by quantitatively assessing the efficacy of these strategies in providing for new performance peaks. Chapter 5 builds on these findings, critically evaluating the effectiveness of these strategies in enhancing the capabilities of LMs for the Citation Intent Classification task. This section aims to provide an answer to the original research question of this work, confirming that the ceiling of some particular Language Models - SciBERT mainly - can be surpassed by a large margin with the application of the strategies utilized in this study. This chapter further elaborates on the theoretical and practical implications of this study, providing for some possible solutions and new pathways to both

overcome the challenges and limitations encountered, and to advance these models even above the new State-Of-The-Art (SOTA) reached within this research.

Finally, Chapter 6 briefly presents a classification tool developed within the GraspOS project and built upon the best performing model obtained within this study. This section details both the main functionalities of the backend architecture, as well as the ease of use of the interface designed for such web application.

7.1. Future Works & Perspectives

This study, beside the production of a granular and modular framework that can be further extended and deployed within a single software for testing LMs capabilities within the CIC task, demonstrated also that the ceiling of yet employed Language Models - in particular in the case of SciBERT - can be further exceeded. As a result of this study, SciBERT base models performances demonstrated an high margin for improvement and, with the possibilities discussed in Chapter 5 and derived from a critical inspection of this research - such as the integration of domain adaptation steps, a study focused on feature ablation, the use of enhanced HP optimization methods, or the implementation of retroactive training of ensembles together with a wider set of base models -, it is possible to think to further enhancements of such models.

7.1.1. Beside the Framework - Future Directions and Novel strategies

Beside the techniques presented here and their possible enhancement, it would be interesting also to integrate other strategies within this framework, and testing the performances of these and other LMs upon them. A valuable example of different methodologies may be based on *In-Context Learning* (Dong et al., 2022; Yousefi et al., 2023) strategies, such as *Zero*, *One*, or *Few-Shot Learning* (Brown et al., 2020) smoothly integrated and compared with *Chain of Thoughts* (Wei et al., 2022; Chu et al., 2023) approaches. These would be particularly interesting to test with the employment of Large Language Models (LLMs) such as the different version of Galactica (Taylor et al., 2022), or other untested models such as T5 (Raffel et al., 2019), Flan-T5 (Chung et al., 2022), PaLM (Chowdhery et al., 2022), and U-PaLM (Tay et al., 2022). Within *In-Context Learning*, limitations on model sizes almost disappear, in particular because the need of computational

resources is limited to inference mode. The employment of such strategies could provide a more detailed understanding of the CIC task and of the relevant semantic aspects of citations for classification purposes. Integrating such techniques within the framework provided is one of the next logical steps to expand the project.

Another possibility involve the integration of Language Models, or of Ensemble strategies, within the broader framework of *Neural-Symbolic Systems* (see **Appendix B.2**) to efficiently solve the CIC task. Within this kind of frameworks it is possible to obtain classifications which are no more solely based on the intrinsic semantics of contexts, but take into consideration also other structured data sources, such as Knowledge Graphs (KG). Indeed, KG for citation data may be extremely informative with respect to possible logical rules contained within them, and the possibility to produce Knowledge Graph Embeddings (KGE) provides the possibility to easily integrate this structured data source with the embeddings produced by means of Language Models (LME). Such integration between KGE and LME may be operated in a multitude of ways, but their delineation goes outside the scope of this work. Nevertheless, approaching the task in a *reasoning for learning* or in a *learning-reasoning* perspective may lead to many advantages. First of all, integrating logical rules and intrinsic semantics of citation contexts should theoretically provide for a more *structured* approach to CIC, and for an enhanced explainability of the obtained results, which is critical to obtain reliable systems to utilize in production environments.

7.2. Final Remarks

Overall, a conclusive perspective on this research finds the CIC domain at a juncture point between the need to understand the academic discourse, which may lead to a better research assessment, and the progress in Natural Language Process (NLP) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) related domains. This work underscored the critical need of a comprehensive and well curated dataset for the CIC task, also providing empirical demonstrations w.r.t. the critical role that the amount and quality of data have in the outcomes that can be obtained. An exemplar demonstration of this is given by the lower performances across *all* models for the Result class of the SciCite dataset, which clearly contains an insufficient number of datapoints for the development of a comprehensive model.

Despite that, the most noteworthy achievement of this work has been the production of an ensemble model which surpasses the State-Of-The-Art (SOTA) for the CIC task within SciCite. This result is extremely promising, in particular in light of the possible enhancements that may derive from the application of the techniques outlined in Chapter 5.

In conclusion, this thesis, which started with the aim of exploring alternative methodologies for the CIC task, produced extremely promising results, paving the way for further enhancements in both surpassing current ceilings, and in the explainability of the resulting classifications, thus providing for interesting research directions to follow within next works. By leveraging the synergies between advanced computational techniques and a deep understanding of scholarly discourse, this work contributes to shape research within the field of Citation Intent Classification, and to the ongoing dialogue within the academic community, providing new building blocks for research assessment tools.

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APPENDIX

Appendix A - Working Mechanics

A.1) Cross-Entropy Loss Function

Here a brief presentation of the Cross-Entropy Loss.

- **Binary cross-entropy loss:**

Cross-Entropy Loss is a widely used loss function in machine learning, particularly for classification problems. It measures the performance of a classification model whose output is a probability value between 0 and 1. Cross-Entropy Loss increases as the predicted probability diverges from the actual label, making it an effective measure for evaluating the accuracy of a classifier. It is especially common in binary classification tasks.

In a binary classification context, the function computes the loss for each instance by considering the true label and the predicted probability, effectively quantifying how far off the prediction is from the actual label. A perfect model would have a cross-entropy loss of zero.

$$\text{Loss} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)]$$

Where:

- N : Number of samples in the dataset.
- y_i : True label of the i^{th} sample. It is 1 if the sample belongs to the class, and 0 otherwise.
- \hat{y}_i : Predicted probability that the i^{th} sample belongs to the class.

- **Weighted Binary cross-entropy loss:**

Weighted Cross-Entropy Loss is an extension of the standard cross-entropy loss function, designed to handle imbalanced datasets where the classes are not equally represented. It works by assigning different weights to each class, typically giving higher weights to less represented classes. This approach helps to balance the model's attention across all classes, ensuring that minority classes are adequately considered and the model does not develop a bias towards the majority class.

$$\text{Loss} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [w_1 y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + w_0 (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)]$$

Where:

- N : Number of samples in the dataset.
- y_i : True label of the i^{th} sample. It is 1 if the sample belongs to the class, and 0 otherwise.
- \hat{y}_i : Predicted probability that the i^{th} sample belongs to the class.
- w_1 and w_0 : Weights for the positive (1) and negative (0) classes, respectively.

• **Categorical cross-entropy loss:**

Categorical Cross-Entropy Loss, also known as Multiclass Cross-Entropy Loss, is used for multi-class classification tasks, where each instance can belong to one of many possible classes. This loss function is similar to binary cross-entropy but is extended to accommodate multiple classes. It compares the predicted probability distribution for each class with the actual distribution (the true labels). In this setting, the loss is calculated for each class of an instance and then summed up, providing a measure of how far the model's predictions are from the actual class labels. The lower the loss, the better the model's predictions are in terms of accuracy and confidence.

$$\text{Loss} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^C y_{ij} \log(\hat{y}_{ij})$$

Where:

- N : Number of samples in the dataset.
- C : Number of classes.
- y_{ij} : Binary indicator (0 or 1) if class j is the correct classification for observation i .
- \hat{y}_i : Predicted probability that the i^{th} sample belongs to the class.

• **Weighted categorical cross-entropy loss:**

Weighted Categorical Cross-Entropy Loss is a variant of categorical cross-entropy designed for imbalanced multi-class datasets. Similar to its binary counterpart, this function assigns weights to each class in a multi-class problem, typically giving higher weights to most rare labels. This weighting scheme ensures that the model pays more attention to the under-represented classes, thus addressing the imbalance and improving the model's overall performance across all classes.

$$\text{Loss} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^C w_j y_{ij} \log(\hat{y}_{ij})$$

Where:

- N : Number of samples in the dataset.
- C : Number of classes.
- w_j : Weight assigned to class j .
- y_{ij} : Binary indicator if label j is the correct classification for observation i .
- \hat{y}_{ij} : Predicted probability of observation i being of class j .

A.2) Population Based Training

This part of Appendix A aims to provide an overview on Population Based Training working dynamics.

Population Based Training (PBT) is an advanced and dynamic hyperparameter tuning optimization strategy that tries to enhance models performances by evolving hyperparameters over time. It combines ideas derived from evolutionary algorithms - thus based on the biological evolutionary theory - and hyperparameter optimization, and it is especially useful for optimizing deep learning models where the training process is computationally demanding.

Here's a breakdown of how PBT works:

1. **Initial Population Creation:** PBT starts by initializing a population of models with varying hyperparameters. This population of models is usually generated in a random manner by providing them some hyperparameters usually selected from within user-specified ranges.
2. **Training and Evaluation:** Each model in the population is trained for a predetermined number of iterations or epochs - the researcher decides. After this training period, the models are evaluated based on a chosen performance metric, such as accuracy or loss.
3. **Selection and Reproduction - Exploitation:** PBT then selects the top-performing models. The selection criteria usually involve some form of performance threshold or ranking. These successful models are considered for reproduction, where their hyperparameters (and sometimes their learned weights) are used to replace those of less successful models in the population. This step is akin to the *survival of the fittest* principle in evolutionary theories.
4. **Perturbation of Hyperparameters - Exploration:** Before or after the reproduction step, the hyperparameters of the selected models are perturbed. This means they are slightly modified - typically randomly within manually defined ranges or percentages - to explore new combinations and prevent the optimization process from stagnating. Perturbation ensures diversity in the population, which is crucial for exploring the hyperparameter space effectively.
5. **Continued Training:** The new generation of models (some with replaced hyperparameters and some with perturbed hyperparameters) continues training. This cycle of training, evaluating,

selecting, perturbing, and reproducing continues for a predefined number of generations or until a stopping criterion is met.

6. **Final Model Selection:** At the end of the process, the best-performing model(s), based on the evaluation metric, are selected. These models, with their evolved hyperparameters, are typically the ones that are going to be used for the final application.

Some key advantages of this methodology are:

- **Exploitation and Exploration utility:** PBT dynamically balances *exploitation* and *exploration* over training epochs - or evaluations, or any other manually defined criteria. Exploitation is achieved by transferring the hyperparameters of successful models to less good models, while exploration is ensured through some random perturbations of hyperparameters of the worst models. These two techniques, in which lies the core of this optimization algorithm, allows PBT to potentially find better hyperparameters with respect to static methods, and to efficiently explore the search space in a non-random manner.
- **Adaptation to Training Dynamics:** Another key advantage of PBT is its ability to adapt hyperparameters in response to the training dynamics of the model. Since hyperparameters can be optimized while the model is being trained, PBT can lead to faster, and often more effective, convergence when compared to traditional methods that search within a predefined set of hyperparameters manually designed before training.

In conclusion, PBT is both an efficient and effective method for hyperparameter search and tuning. This approach is particularly useful in scenarios where the optimal set of hyperparameters may change over the course of training, and the computational resources are a main concern. Finally, it is well-suited for complex models and/or large datasets, where traditional hyperparameter tuning methods can be prohibitively expensive or ineffective.

Appendix B - Taxonomies

B.1) LMs: SLMs, NLMs, PLMs, and LLMs - A brief distinction

This appendix aims to delineate the distinctions among Language Models (LMs), Pre-trained Language Models (PLMs), and Large Language Models (LLMs), which are pivotal in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP). Understanding these categories may help to grasp the scope and capabilities of various models employed in different NLP tasks, including but not limited to, text classification, sentiment analysis, and question-answering systems.

Language Models are computational models that predict the probability distribution of sequences of words, and are central in NLP for generating and understanding textual data. LMs learn from a corpus of text to predict the likelihood of a sequence of words based on the words that precede them (this really depends on the language modeling objective and on the specific training strategy adopted). This ability enables LMs to perform tasks like text completion, translation, and text generation.

Besides this general definition, it is possible to categorize LMs into four main classes. The first class represents Statistical language models (SLMs), which are developed according to statistical learning methods. Within this category falls the class of *n-gram* models, which see text as a sequence of words and tries to estimate the probability of it as the product of word probabilities (Zhao et al., 2023; Minaee et al., 2024).

The second class is represented by Neural Language Models (NLMs), and is characterized by the computing of the probability of word sequences by means of neural networks (e.g. RNNs). Differently from SLMs, NLMs can deal with data sparsity. Indeed, such models map words to low-dimensional representations (embedding vectors), thus becoming able to predict the next word based on the aggregation of the embedding vectors of its proceeding words using neural networks. Thanks to the hidden space where are represented the embeddings, it is possible to compute semantic similarity tasks. Despite that, NLMs are still task-specific (Zhao et al., 2023; Minaee et al., 2024).

With the third category, represented by Pre-trained Language Models, it is now possible to have a task-agnostic model, and their training and inference follows the *pre-training* and *fine-tuning* paradigm. Within this, language models equipped with recurrent or Transformer (Valenzuela et al. 2017) blocks are first pre-trained on huge text corpora, becoming capable of solving general tasks by means of the pre-trained context-aware word representations (context-aware embeddings), and then fine-tuned for specific tasks using small amounts of data (Zhao et al., 2023; Minaee et al., 2024). Some examples of PLMs are BERT (Devlin et al., 2018), GPT (Radford et al., 2018), or XLNet (Yang et al., 2019), these models represented a significant step within the NLP domain.

By scaling PLMs (model size, or data quantity, or both), the fourth category is obtained. This category is represented by Large Language Models (LLMs), mainly presenting Transformer-based architectures with billion of parameters. Some exemplar LLMs are such as PaLM (Chowdhery et al., 2022), LLaMA (Touvron et al., 2023), or GPT-4 (Achiam et al., 2023). Compared to PLMs, LLMs are thus much larger in terms of parameters, but these models also exhibit better language understanding capabilities, which lead to better generation abilities. Finally, LLMs also show emergent abilities that are not present in smaller-scale language models, such as the ability of “*reasoning*” (Wei et al., 2022; Chu et al., 2023) or the possibility to be fine-tuned without a real weight adjustments of their parameters, such as in *in-context* learning (Wei et al., 2022; Chu et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2023; Minaee et al., 2024).

In conclusion, while all these models play, or have played, crucial roles in advancing the NLP domain, the evolution from early SLMs to PLMs, and further to LLMs, represents a significant leap in the ability of these models to process and understand natural language.

B.2) Neural-Symbolic Learning Systems - Taxonomy of Methods

This appendix aims to briefly present the three main approaches within Neural-Symbolic Learning Systems, hybrid models that leverage the strengths of both *neural systems* and *symbolic systems* by seamlessly integrating symbolic inference and statistical learning (Garcez et al., 2015). The goal of such hybrid systems is to learn symbolic rules while applying neural networks to guide the exploration towards the combinatorial search space (Daniele et al., 2022), in order to obtain a final output based on both learning and reasoning capabilities of the system.

Symbolic systems operate on structured data, such as logic rules, knowledge graphs, or time series data, and within this structure they operate by processing *Symbols*. This kind of systems are trained in order to search within a solution space, and their training is aimed at solving a specific task by means of a *reasoning process* (Yu et al., 2021). On the other hand, neural systems are designed to approximate a function by operating on unstructured data such as images or texts, and such operations are based on *vectors*, which are the main information unit of this kind of systems. By integrating these two components, it is possible to obtain a system that achieves an unitary and comprehensive approach to problem solving, by leveraging the strengths of the two base systems. This hybrid processor tries to map a function $F(x, s) \rightarrow y, \forall (x, y) \in D$ (x is the input, y the desired output, s represents a symbol, and D is the dataset/datasource), which incorporates both symbolic reasoning and statistical inference (Yu et al., 2021; Daniele et al., 2022).

Within the broad domain of Neural-Symbolic Systems, it is possible to discern three main approaches. The following description draws from the survey of Yu and colleagues (2021):

- **Learning for Reasoning:** within this framework the core is represented by the symbolic system, while the neural system is instrumental to either accelerate computations by reducing the search space of the main system, thus it replaces more traditional reasoning algorithms; or it is employed to acquire knowledge, thus extract symbols from unstructured data, in order to then feed the symbolic reasoning process.

- **Reasoning for learning:** here the core part is represented by neural systems, while the symbolic systems are instrumental to support the learning process. In this framework, symbolic knowledge is integrated in the training of Neural Networks to increase performances and enhance the interpretability of the results. For example, symbolic knowledge may be extracted and integrated as a regularization term in the loss function, thereby giving more information within the learning process.
- **Learning-reasoning:** in this third, and last, category, the integration of the two systems is bidirectional, with both having equal importance within the resulting process, where the output of a system becomes the input of the other in a cyclical way, allowing for enhancing the performances of both the systems at once. An example may involve the generation of predictions by the neural system, which are then fed to the symbolic system that operates logical reasoning on them. The results obtained are given back to the neural system, which can adjust its predictions, and so on.

With this the examination on Neural-Symbolic Systems is concluded.

